

Hidepark

**IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellbeing
In small and medium size ciTies**

D 4.1. Inclusive transformation plan of Nitra

Nitra's Pilot

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D4.1 Inclusive Transformation Plan of Nitra

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

Page	Description
3	Update of the Executive Summary to introduce changes to the deliverable and response to rejection letter pertaining to D4.1.
41	Inclusion of table providing quantitative data on co-design process and number of participants for each activity organised.
44 - 47	Inclusion of table with more details provided for hard VIS: photos of current situation at location of deployment and links to specific subdimensions of IHW .
48	Timeline and plan for soft VIS co-deployment for year 2022.
97 - 122	Updated co-deployment timeline for hard VIS to reflect changes from 2/2022 until 9/2022.

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Executive summary

D4.1 Inclusive Transformation Plan of Nitra introduces the methodology, processes and results of two-ways (top-down and bottom-up) co-design process of conceptualization of inclusive transformation plan of Nitra pilot as described in WP4, Task 4.2 of the Grant Agreement. First part of the document details the stakeholder engagement and community activation process carried out in Task 4.1 resulting in establishment of Nitra IN-HUB as a PPPP (public-private-people partnership) type living laboratory under the guidance of partner TSR. Second part of the document details the top-down and bottom-up co-design processes carried out by the partners SUA, HIDE and NITRA and institutional stakeholders and community representatives with various degree of involvement in the Nitra IN-HUB. Third part of the document lists hard and soft visionary and integrated solutions that emerged as a result of the co-design process, as well as plans and modes for their co-deployment and co-management. The last part reflects on challenges faced by the Nitra partners in carrying out the aforementioned tasks and detailed risk assessment analysis as a basis for their mitigation and formulation of recommendation both general and city specific. Inclusive Transformation Plan of Nitra is an open and flexible document, subject to revisions according to changing local situation, possible future amendments on the project level, and emerging challenges in future co-design, co-deployment and co-management process.

D4.1 Inclusive Transformation Plan of Nitra was updated in September 2022 to reflect comments and suggestion raised during the review process. Changes include adding more clear representation on number of participants and involved stakeholders during co-design process, along with more clear presentation on the involvement of different target groups. It is necessary to note, that data on involvement of minority and other specific target groups is only possible to provide for the co-design process, namely the structure of different sections of Nitra IN-HUB (Table 2 on page 14) not all of the soft activities deployed during this period, as collection of relevant personal data needed to do so was not possible. Detailed description of VIS is provided, as it was in the previous iteration of the ITPlan in appendices 14 and 15 (pages 97 – 129). Action plan and timeframe is provided for each hard VIS separately in sections titled “Co-deployment timeline” on pages 97 – 122. These sections were updated to reflect changes in proposed timeline for all VIS from February 2022 to September 2022. Business models for implementation of each hard and soft VIS are detailed in sections co-deployment and co-management on pages 97 – 129. To provide a more complete picture of the co-designed hard VIS, photodocumentation of the location where they will be deployed was provided along with the expected links to different sub-dimensions if inclusive health and well-being. Additionally, we also include a detailed timeframe for the soft activities planned for year 2022.

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1. Introduction

Nitra is the 6th largest city of Slovakia with total of 78 353 (2020) inhabitants, covering an area of 100.48 square kilometers. In terms of settlement structure of the Slovak Republic, the city of Nitra is defined as a centre of superregional to nationwide importance and in some specific functions of international importance. It is considered an important growth pole in regional context.

City of Nitra is dubbed as a location of the largest agricultural centre of the Slovak Republic. It is located in the Danube Lowland, which has a **strong agricultural tradition**. Aside from concentration of food processing industry, Slovak Agricultural University resides here as the only agricultural university in Slovakia as well as other research institutions.

The **economic base of the city is predominantly industrial**, namely engineering industry (machine and tools production, production of electronic and mechanical appliances, etc.), electrical engineering, woodworking industry, textile industry and food processing industry. The landscape of Nitra and its surroundings as well as demographic situation changed considerably in the last three decades. During this period Nitra experienced net population loss (since 1997 Nitra lost almost 6.4 thousand residents). The leading causes were **suburbanization processes as well as outmigration** from the region (as evidenced by the positive migration balance in the district and negative migration balance in the region and the city itself pictured in Figure 1.4 in Annex 1). In recent years, however, due to arrival of Jaguar Land Rover (but also other large employers), this trend was reversed, mainly as a result of foreign immigration (see Figure 1.4 in Annex 1).

The city itself is dubbed a **university city**, with more than 12,000 students studying at two universities located here. However, the city also earned a nickname of a **“transit station”** especially for younger population. Although Nitra’s universities are capable of attracting young talent from all regions of Slovakia the city itself is not able to retain them upon graduation (their origin and current residence is pictured in Figure 1.5 in Annex 1). Only 8.7% of those who came to Nitra to attend the university stays here after finishing their studies, but what is even more alarming 37% of Nitra natives studying here decides to leave upon graduation (university stayers and late migrants in Figure 1.6 in Annex 1 respectively).

Although most of the city’s population are Slovak nationals and native born (as evidenced by Figure 1.1 in Annex 1), there is a continually **growing immigrant community**. The whole of Nitra region has experienced the greatest increase of foreign migrants out of all of Slovak regions (59% between 2018/2019). Most of them are concentrated in the city of Nitra. Figure 1.2 in Annex 1 shows the origin of total of 5.143 migrants registered in Nitra in 2019. About half are from EU/ECC countries and half from non-EU/ECC countries. Most are from Ukraine, Romania, Bulgaria, Serbia and other Balkan countries. This number is underestimated, since relatively large percentage of those from less developed countries are so called “three-month-migrants” (they do not obtain a regular residence permit but rather work on a three-month intervals). Thus, some estimates indicate that about 10,000 foreign economic migrants come to Nitra each year. The economic activities and the influx of foreign investors are **having negative effects on the city’s health and wellbeing**: increased pressure on existing facilities and services, housing market, congestion in

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central part of the city, higher production of air pollutants, permanent noise and reduced quality of life in the vicinity of traffic corridors. Housing and integration for immigrant workers is now an outstanding problem in Nitra. Some investors took action to build lodging houses, even within the industrial areas themselves, which lead to low living standards and quality of life, isolation (both geographical and socio-economic) and subsequent emergence of a number of socio-pathological behaviours. Negative consequences of this situation are further exacerbated by the fact that majority of migrant workers in the industrial park are men (nearly 70%), who are not followed to Nitra by their families¹ and 45% seek only a temporary residence (as indicated in Figure 1.3 of Annex 1). This contributes significantly to their isolation and difficult integration into the community and potential clash between the newcomers and local population.

Part of the city, which is one of the most affected by this expansion is the city **district Dražovce**, near which the newest **Industrial Park – North** was built on a greenfield. This neighbourhood is to a large degree disjointed from the main city, having been a separate municipality until 1975. Additionally, in contrast to the rest of the city, it retained its rural characteristics, dominant values, norms and way of life. As depicted in Annex 2, the neighbourhood experienced an increase in physical isolation in recent years due to redevelopment of adjacent green spaces into industrial areas. Dražovce district is a small residential area with only 1,874 inhabitants. Table 2.1 in Annex 2 provides basic population characteristics of the neighbourhood², according to which, the share of population 64+ is lower than in the rest of the city. However, available data are skewed due to the presence of a large community of Roma living in the neighbourhood who tend to have younger age structure. In contrast, Slovak majority living in the neighbourhood experiences population aging. According to the last available population census (2011), 89% of Nitra City population is of Slovak ethnicity, while only 0,66% declared to be of Roma descent. This number is underestimated, since majority of Roma either do not declare ethnicity or declare to be ethnic Slovaks or Hungarians. One of the largest Roma communities is concentrated in Dražovce district. They experience low living standards, social, economic and spatial exclusion as depicted in Annex 2. This led to a gradual spatial segregation, best illustrated by fencing of the local elementary school almost exclusively attended by Roma children with barbwire fence by adjacent property owners. The elementary school, often referred to by part of the local population as “the major thing that keeps Roma here, thus should be closed” is severely underfunded, lacking even the school canteen. Most of the children opt to eat traditionally less

¹ This trend is slowly starting to change, as entire families are starting to immigrate to Nitra.

² Neighbourhood is not a separate administrative unit, thus more detailed relevant data for the neighbourhood is not available.

healthy food typical for the Roma community, compounding on other factors negatively affecting their health and wellbeing.

Figure 1 Residence of visitors to cultural and recreational spaces in the pilot area

Source: own elaboration based on questionnaire data

most of the landfill was removed, there are still unrevitalized areas with layers of waste, uneven terrain that could be used to develop missing elements and increase the capacity of the community centre, which is insufficient given the rate of attendance and demand. Although the utilities like drinking water and sewage system run along the community centre, the community centre is still not connected. They also report major decrease in volunteers willing to take part in their activities.

The city is trying to resolve the problems of congestion, mobility and geographical isolation of the Dražovce neighbourhood and the alternative transport accessibility of the industrial park by promoting alternative modes of transport, mainly bicycle transport. To this end, the city is completing an **8 km cyclotraffic corridor linking the Dražovce neighbourhood, the industrial park with the City Park and the city centre and Hídepark along the riverbank of the Nitra River**. Although cycling trails are being built as alternative modes of transport, they are still underused by residents of Nitra and employees in the industrial

Locations in Nitra pilot area that are frequented by listed vulnerable groups and where they interact with other target groups are the **City Park** (the largest green area within the city limits, frequented by residents from all parts of Nitra, providing public spaces for various leisure activities and other functional use) and Hídepark. **Hídepark** is a grassroots open-space community and cultural centre established on a site of former illegal landfill. It originated in 2010, with a group of young people revitalizing the site that grew into a fully-fledged cultural and community centre. The place is currently used by more than 10 organizations and groups: NGOs, non-profit organizations, civic associations, foundations, interest groups active in fields such as culture and art, sport, ecology, education, etc. It is considered to be a safe space for social interaction and leisure activities by various target and vulnerable groups. However, the centre has recently experienced a number of limiting barriers for its proper functioning and further development. Although opened throughout entire year, due to its “open air” character, most of the activities are concentrated from May to September. Although

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park, who consider cycling to be dangerous and ineffective (Sustainable Mobility Plan of Nitra City from 2018 lists only 0,96% of instances using bicycle as a means of travel to work, compared to 66% using car). Additionally there is a lack of cycling micro-infrastructure.

Initial objective of the Nitra pilot was to **improve healthy lifestyles, social inclusion of migrants and ethnic minorities, social cohesion and relational well-being** among people living in Dražovce neighbourhood, working in the Industrial Park or frequenting areas along the 8 km cycle road connecting Dražovce with the city centre.

The specific objectives are the following:

- to increase healthy habits among local people, particularly the most vulnerable (low income people and groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion) by reducing sedentary lifestyles, social isolation and increasing intergenerational and intercultural relations;
- to improve the quality of the urban public space in terms of safety, accessibility, inclusiveness, liveability (air quality, temperature, presence of green areas and leisure/sports facilities);
- to enhance skills and competences, networking and organizational capacity of local changemakers, especially NGOs active in the socio-cultural field.

The main innovative concept that will generate value added of Nitra pilot is a combination of visionary and integrated solutions (social innovation, cultural innovation, NBS solutions and digital and technological innovations) into the **REMOULD** concept – **Reversible Multifunctional Open-source Urban LanDscape**.

REMOULD is an urban planning approach aimed at integrating public, residential and commercial spaces (as illustrated by Figure 2) in a transformable and adaptable way to the changing needs of the area:

- **REversible** – transformable and adaptable to the changing needs, sensitive to the environment,
- **Multifunctional** – milieu integrating activities and people of diverse backgrounds and interests, resource efficient,
- **Open-source** – customizable, living, organic space with specific uses assigned by the users themselves thus increasing the sense of ownership of public and common spaces,
- **Urban LanDscape** - not only a physical environment with built elements, but also an atmosphere inspired and defined by people, cultures, art and nature.

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Figure 2 Nitra pilot area and the REMOULD zones

In Nitra pilot, IN-HABIT project will build (co-design, co-deploy and co-manage) the REMOULD concept based on **mobilizing two main existing undervalued resources** to boost inclusive health and wellbeing and respond to challenges described above and throughout this document: **art and environment**.

The co-design of REMOULD requires participation of landscape architects, artists, migrants, students, social entrepreneurs, relevant organisations and local residents. The co-deployment process will rely strongly on the DIY culture of the community, while co-management and economic sustainability is promoted through innovative business models. The flexibility of the REMOULD approach also increases the replicability of co-designed and co-deployed VIS.

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2. IN-HUB establishment: organization, methods and achievements

2.1. Establishment of core project team & stakeholder mapping

The core project team comprises of several departments, labs, research groups and individuals of the three city partners: Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra, City of Nitra and cultural and community centre Hidepark.

Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra (**SUA**), representing academic and research and development sector, serves as the leader of WP4 and its related tasks. Researchers from Institute of Regional and Local Development (Faculty of European Studies and Regional Development – FESRD) provide overall project coordination on the local level, coordinate conceptualisation of methodologies, communication with transversal partners on IN-HABIT project level and general public on the national and city level and is responsible for carrying out monitoring and evaluation activities in cooperation with other involved persons and entities, co-deployment and co-management of selected VIS, dissemination towards policy representatives on local, regional, national and European level. It also employs one of the LCAs. Researchers at the Institute of Landscape Architecture (Faculty of Horticulture and Landscape Engineering – FHLE), Institute of Environmental Management (FESRD), and Botanical Garden are leading the co-design process and are actively involved in the co-deployment and partially co-management process of VIS in Nitra pilot. Researchers at the Laboratory of Modelling of Urban Environment and Landscape (Research centre AgroBioTech) in cooperation with other institutes analyse the results and output of the co-design process and prepare technical documentation for hard VIS.

Community and cultural centre Hidepark (**HIDE**) as a grassroots NGO initiative is a co-leader of the task 4.4 Co-management of Nitra VIS and will actively participate in co-deployment of selected VIS, applying their extensive experience in volunteer based approaches do-it-yourself mind-sets and experience working with vulnerable groups (children, migrants etc.). HIDE partner also represents an already established and growing nexus of diverse stakeholders active in all thematic sub-groups (see chapter 2.3), thus being crucial during the stakeholder mapping, engagement process and establishment of the Nitra IN-HUB and coordination of its activities. As a results, one of the LCA positions is fulfilled by HIDE partner.

City of Nitra (**NITRA**) represents local municipal self-government with competencies and jurisdiction within several themes covered by Nitra pilot planned VIS. City partner coordinates their tasks through the Project and Strategic Management Department. Head of the department is responsible for facilitating communication with other public and institutional stakeholders on the city and regional level, while the Officer for Urban Development and Sustainable Economy is responsible for facilitating communication between project partners, Core IN-HUB (see chapter 2.3) and relevant departments of the city administration with competencies and jurisdiction in education, culture, social services, environment, transportation and mobility and urban development and spatial planning, aiding in carrying out tasks related to monitoring and evaluation activities, planning collaborative modes of co-deployment and co-

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management and is responsible for replication and dissemination of project results in other neighbourhoods of the city.

Core project team members were the starting point of the stakeholder mapping process. The process started in September – October 2020, when the team conducted two-stage snowball sampling social network analysis with egocentric approach (Figure 3.1 in Annex 3). In the first stage, the three core project partners identified stakeholders and their potential area of contribution/involvement in promoting visionary and integrated solutions to boost IHW in Nitra in general and pilot area specifically (either already collaborating or those they knew of). In the second stage those identified stakeholders identified further stakeholders and their potential contribution and area of involvement³. This multiple-stage process is open-ended and continuously updates the scope of stakeholder involvement (Figures 3.2 – 3.4 in Annex 3 show gradual establishment and changes to the structure of the Nitra IN-HUB). Current state of the stakeholder mapping and with references to the structure of the Nitra IN-HUB is illustrated by Figure 3.5 in Annex 3.

2.2. Open call and communication campaign to select the members of the local IN-HUB

“The IN-HUB is a laboratory of social innovation where people coming from different public and private organisations or as individual citizens work together for social change. It is a networking strategy for the enhancement of cooperation aimed at the co-design and co-management of spaces and a platform for structural dialogue and collaboration. IN-HUBs are both physical places for meeting and sharing, and organisational structures to facilitate the transformative process”⁴. IN-HUB Nitra was built on the principles of polycentric governance and Public-Private-People Partnership, in order to create a more inclusive governance involving different actors, addressing the problems of exclusion and lack of transparency, including citizens’ knowledge, more effectively and creating environments and services that respond better to the needs of inhabitants. Process of informing, contacting and recruiting potential members of Nitra IN-HUB was governed by the strong focus on the Gender, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (GDEI) perspective of the IN-HABIT approach to health and wellbeing promotion. It was adapted to local conditions to reflect the core values of Nitra pilot (art and environment) and to reach specifically these overlapping categories:

- **vulnerable groups** (ethnic minorities and migrants, persons with disabilities, children and elderly etc.);
- **institutional stakeholders and active people** in fields of Social and Community Innovations, Art and Cultural Innovations, Healthy Lifestyle, Sport and Alternative Mobility Modes, Education, Nature Based Solutions, Digital, Architectonic and Technical Innovations, with pilot area and city-wide scope;

³ Only the institutional, not individual stakeholders are shown in Annex 3

⁴ IN-HABIT Glossary

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- **specific groups of pilot area users** (namely residents of Dražovce, employees of the industrial park, visitors of cultural and community centre Hidepark, recreational cyclists, those that use cycling as a means of transport, fishermen, land owners etc.).

Communication campaign ran alongside the stakeholder mapping. Given both territorial and thematic scope of the Nitra pilot, traditional mass-media communication channels were less effective. They were dubbed by potential IN-HUB members as not very suitable to clearly communicate relatively new and complicated approach to some of the target groups and too impersonal to elicit active interest. This is why the communication campaign relied heavily on the contact databases, private and professional contacts and networks of initial and subsequently identified stakeholders, both institutional and individual, word-of-mouth and targeting specific communities. For example institutional stakeholders we contacted through network of contacts of Hidepark community, Nitra Volunteer Organisation (with database of over 700 registered volunteers and 60 cooperating organisations), Nitra Community Foundation, COMIN – Community Centre for Labour and Knowledge Mobility Nitra and their First Contact Point database and Mareena NGO to reach migrant communities, Roma ambassador of the City of Nitra⁵, Regional representative of plenipotentiary of the Government of the Slovak Republic for the Roma community, local schools to reach the Roma community, using identified key contacts in Dražovce neighbourhood (e.g. administrator of private Facebook group “Dražovce” with 415 members/quarter of the population) etc.

IN-HABIT Nitra pilot was introduced during public online discussions led by the Nitra City and Nitra 2026 Association on 29.4.2021 with topic “*Nitra as a Transit Station: Why are young people leaving Nitra?*” and on 27.5.2021 with topic “*Foreigners in Nitra: How do they perceive the city?*”. We joined online discussion with Nitra citizens on 30.3.2021 organised by Office of Chief Architect of Nitra to launch the participative process of designing the new Nitra City Urban Plan. Official IN-HABIT project local press launch took place on 14.10.2021⁶.

2.3. Assignment of specific roles (local community activators/representatives, UAB, thematic sub-groups) and their activities

Launch of the Nitra IN-HUB was more of a process than a specific point in time. Along with already described stakeholder mapping process during second half of 2020 and first half of 2021, individual bilateral consultations and negotiations with prospective IN-HUB members took place. On the **1st of August 2021**, the initiating launch took place in the pilot area at Hidepark community and cultural centre with 11 initial members present, both individual and representatives of institutional stakeholders. IN-HUB Nitra organisational structure is presented in Annex 4 and Table 1 below.

⁵ This position no longer exists

⁶ <https://tvnitricka.sk/novy-europsky-projekt/>

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Table 1 IN-HUB Nitra organisational structure

<p>Institutional Support and Oversight</p>					
<p>IN-HABIT partner organisations</p> <p>SUA WP4 local coordinator LCA – facilitation of research related tasks KLC – communication and dissemination Co-design facilitator</p> <p>Botanical Garden Nitra (SUA) – co-design and co-deployment, AgroBioTech (SUA) – preparation of technical documentation for VIS</p> <p>NITRA Project and Strategic Management Department</p> <p>HIDE LCA – IN-HUB facilitator</p>	<p>UAB – stakeholder representatives</p> <p>NGO Cuketa NGO “Let’s Cycle Nitra!” NGO Mareena NGO STORM Independent Atelier 37 Pomáhajko, NGO Creative centre Nitra NGO Pestrec NGO Icebears NGO District NGO HidePumpa Elementary school Dražovce Elementary school Tulipánová</p>	<p>Department of Education – coordinator for work with Roma minority</p> <p>Department of Culture</p> <p>Department of Environment</p> <p>Department of Social Services – Community Planning Officer</p> <p>Department of Transportation – mobility referent</p> <p>Office of Chief Architect of Nitra City</p> <p>Slovak Water Management Company, state enterprise - SVP</p> <p>Regional representative of Plenipotentiary of the Government of the Slovak Republic for the Roma Community</p> <p>Ministry of Transport and Construction - New European Bauhaus National Contact Point</p>			
<p>Affiliated Stakeholders</p>					
<p>COMIN – Community Centre for Labour and Knowledge Mobility Nitra Nitra Community Foundation Architects Association Nitra Nitra Volunteer Centre Internat. Theatre festival “Divadelná Nitra” KINOKLUB Initiative Night run Nitra</p>	<p>NGO Drum show NGO I Care NGO IRV/ROK Episcopacy Nitra Elementary Art School ATELIER MEDEA Secondary School of Art Design Adoreal, llc</p>	<p>Arriva, a.s. Sekáč Jaguar Land Rover MH Invest, llc Západoslovenská vodárenská spoločnosť, a.s. Creative Centre SPU Department of Ethnology and Folklore Studies UCF</p>			
<p>Advisory Groups</p>					
<p>Digital, Architectonic, Technical Innovations</p>					

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Core IN-HUB Nitra: is comprised of representatives of IN-HABIT project partners (Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra, Hidepark Community and Cultural Centre and City of Nitra) and individual and institutional representatives of key stakeholders. Community stakeholders in Core IN-HUB represent the role of User Advisory Board. Along with 13 institutional stakeholders with city-wide scope (aside from NGO Pomáhajko and involved schools that are neighbourhood organisations), 17 individual stakeholder are involved. Profiles of institutional members of UAB are listed in Annex 5.

They were chosen to cover:

- 1) vulnerable, disadvantaged and other target groups as defined in D7.3 Baseline Study on IHW (young students aged 18 – 30, persons with disabilities, women, LGBTQI+ people, elderly aged 65+, persons living alone, ethnic minorities, migrants, religious minorities) as represented in Table 2;

Table 2 List and profiles of individual UAB members

Stakeholder	Target groups (member or works with)							
	Women	Migrants and ethnic minorities	Students	Persons with Disabilities and other vulnerable groups	Elderly	Persons living alone	LGBTQI+	Special users of the pilot are (eg. cyclists)
Person A	x							x
Person B	x							x
Person C								x
Person D								x
Person E	x							x
Person F	x	x	x					
Person G		x						
Person H	x	x						
Person I	x	x		x				
Person J				x		x		
Person K	x				x			
Person L	x	x				x		
Person M	x			x				
Person N	x							
Person O			x				x	
Person P	x		x					x
Person R				x		x		

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- 2) communities living, working or using different spaces within the pilot area (residential district Dražovce, Industrial Park North, City Park, Cultural and Community Centre Hidepark and cyclo-corridor connecting all of these as illustrated in Figure 2) as represented in Table 3;

Table 3 List and profiles of individual UAB members

Stakeholder	Pilot area focus				
	Residential District Dražovce	Industrial Park North	Cultural and Community Centre Hidepark	City Park	Cyclo-corridor and river
Person A			X	X	X
Person B			X		X
Person C				X	X
Person D	X				X
Person E					X
Person F	X	X	X	X	X
Person G		X		X	
Person H		X		X	
Person I	X	X	X	X	X
Person J			X		
Person K	X			X	X
Person L			X	X	
Person M	X	X			
Person N	X				
Person O	X				X
Person P			X	X	X
Person R			X	X	X

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3) themes and values that IN-HABIT project covers in Nitra as represented in Table 4.

Table 4 Roles of institutional UAB members in Advisory Groups

Stakeholder	Social and Community Innovations	Art and Cultural Innovations	Healthy Lifestyle, Sport, Alternative Mobility Modes	Education	Nature Based Solutions	Digital, Architectonic and Technical Innovations
NGO CUKETA				x	x	x
NGO “Let's Cycle Nitra!”			x			x
NGO Mareena	x	x		x		
NGO STORM	x					
Independent Atelier 37		x				x
Pomáhajko, NGO	x					
Creative centre Nitra		x				x
OZ Pestrec				x	x	
Botanical Garden					x	
AgroBioTech					x	x
Elementary school Dražovce	x			x	x	
Elementary school Tulipánová	x			x	x	
HidePumpa NGO			x			
Ice bears NGO	x		x			
District NGO		x				x

Facilitating the functioning of Nitra IN-HUB are two local community activators. They support local stakeholders/citizen engagement, identifying community leaders, networks and organisations. LCA employed by the partner **HIDE** is responsible for reaching out to people living and working in the area, with specific attention to those at risk of exclusion and discrimination, in order to engage them in co-designing and co-creating project solutions, organising co-design workshops and communicating with Affiliated Stakeholders group. LCA employed by the **SUA** partner supports university teams and other

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project partner organisations in desk and field research: taking care of secondary data collection through networking with local private and public entities; translating and making reports on data collection; taking care of primary data collection through interviews, questionnaires, workshops and focus groups and writing down the related reports. Roles of other people and positions at partner SUA are explained in Chapter 2.1. Officer for Urban Development and Sustainable Economy employed at the Project and Strategic Management Department of partner **NITRA** is responsible for facilitating communication with Institutional Support and Oversight section of IN-HUB, carrying tasks related to checking compliance with relevant city-wide policies, seeking necessary approvals, aiding the co-deployment process and facilitating data collection in desk and field research.

Affiliated Stakeholders: represent representatives of mostly institutional stakeholders in the pilot area or the city that expressed their interest to be a part of the project and have aligned goals with IN-HABIT project, with whom cooperation can bring mutual benefits, e.g. cooperation on co-deployment and/or co-management of only limited specific solutions that are part of planned VIS, but do not have time or personnel capacity to be full members of the Core IN-HUB Nitra (attend regular and frequent meetings with Core IN-HUB members). This group also encompasses several stakeholders with various ownership relations and rights in the pilot area. Communication with this group of stakeholders is carried mostly on need-based ad-hoc bilateral basis. Profiles of affiliated stakeholders are listed in Annex 6.

Institutional Support and Oversight: represents policy representatives and representatives of (mostly) public entities on municipal, regional and national level that have jurisdiction or other vested interest in the specific themes and topics covered by the IN-HABIT project in Nitra pilot, but were not able to join the Core IN-HUB. Communication with this group of stakeholders is carried mostly on need-based ad-hoc bilateral basis. Their role is mostly to safeguard alignment of IN-HABIT project processes and results (mostly those related to co-design, co-deployment and co-management) with their respective policy priorities and requirements. Over the course of the co-design process some stakeholders crossed from this group into affiliated stakeholders (by taking more active part in the co-design and planned co-deployment and co-management of VIS).

Members of all three section of IN-HUB Nitra formed **6 Advisory Groups** based on their respective fields of action, interests within the scope of IN-HABIT project, or involvement in co-design and co-deployment of specific VIS, namely: Social and Community Innovations AG, Art and Cultural Innovations AG, Healthy Lifestyle, Sport, Alternative Mobility Modes AG, Education AG, Nature Based Solutions AG, and Digital, Architectonic and Technical Innovations AG. No separate Advisory Group or other body specifically focused on health and wellbeing was formed. Rather different dimensions of health and wellbeing are discussed as a horizontal priority in each of the Advisory Groups.

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2.4. Setting up principles, procedures, and processes of collaborative development and participation

IN-HUB Nitra took shape of an informal living lab without separate legal identity. Its current organisational structure developed gradually and organically as a result of the stakeholder engagement and VIS co-design process.

Representatives of the IN-HABIT project partners SUA, HIDE and NITRA meet on a regular basis, while the Core IN-HUB group meets at least once in three months, or more regularly if necessary. Meetings with affiliated stakeholders and representatives of Institutional Support and Oversight group are conducted individually. Advisory Groups for specific themes meet ad-hoc to discuss specific VIS. These meetings were more frequent, but less formal with lower level of organisation. Both regular and ad-hoc meetings were initiated mostly by the representatives of the project partners, however dates, times and places of the meetings are always adapted to the conditions and requirements of the UAB stakeholders. Namely, most of the members of UAB (even those representing institutional stakeholders) are full-time employees of different organisations since non-profit sector in Slovakia is less professionalized, thus they are unable to meet during regular office hours. To accommodate them, meetings were held mostly in the afternoon, in the evening or during the weekends. Places where meeting are held were also chosen in respect to the UAB members' requirements.

Incentives for participations were not used extensively. Most of the involved stakeholders became members or chose to participate due to the alignment of their needs, priorities or interest with the objectives of IN-HABIT project and Nitra pilot. However, their degree of involvement varies. For example, in terms of co-design process several UAB members (an elderly women from Dražovce residential area, local charitable activist from Dražovce, pair of migrants working in the industrial park) took initiative on their own and ran separate co-design activities with local groups that IN-HABIT partners were not able to reach (e.g. relatively large group of women on maternity leave living in the area who decided not to get vaccinated). They subsequently relayed the information to the IN-HUB. This is why project partners are exploring options of providing monetary or other incentives for those members who are more actively involved in the project since their activities outside of the planned IN-HUB meetings were invaluable to the co-design process, especially during the heights of the pandemic.

Overall, principles and procedures that were set up during this period were greatly affected by the restrictions placed due to the COVID-19 pandemic (as detailed in Annex 7) and were planned around imposed restrictions or other limitations.

Due to the relatively large territorial scope of Nitra pilot, as well as it containing vastly different neighbourhoods with different functional use (residential area, industrial park, recreational and cultural areas), that does not have a clear spatial demarcation and its borders are rather fuzzy, formalizing and institutionalizing especially decision making procedures within the Nitra IN-HUB was rather difficult. During the evolvement of the IN-HUB, both IN-HABIT partners and UAB members agreed that decision

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on specific topics or VIS concerning only certain stakeholders should be done on a bilateral basis, while final decisions about VIS to be deployed should be based on seeking a consensus among all stakeholders.

3. Co-design of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS): top-down driven process

3.1. Working methods and management of the Toolkit

The IN-HABIT Toolkit aims to provide a set of guidelines, methods and tools for the wider engagement of stakeholders in the People-public-private partnerships (PPPPs). It includes instructions for stakeholders mapping and local needs assessment, selection criteria, structure, working rules and diversity management procedures, co-design methodology, and the necessary guidelines and templates for the creation and management of the four local IN-HUBs. The Toolkit is the basis for the training process of the Local Community Activators and provides the reference set for the management of the four local IN-HUBS established in the cities of Córdoba, Lucca, Nitra, and Riga. It supports the accomplishment of a fully inclusive process of co-creation, co-design, co-management, and co-monitoring of the innovative solutions envisioned by the four local PPPPs, with specific attention at the engagement of stakeholders less represented and more at risk of exclusion.

The toolkit includes:

- Glossary, providing definitions of the main terms adopted by the project as agreed among the partners,
- Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (GDEI) guidelines, aimed at supporting the wider, just and equal participation of all social groups to the process,
- IN-HUBs Management guidelines, which provide tools and templates for setting the local PPPPs coordination structure, co-monitoring procedures, and to support the co-creation of innovative solutions with citizens and stakeholders.

IN-HABIT Glossary developed by transversal partner TSR was invaluable in the process of explaining certain concepts that are core to the IN-HABIT project during the stakeholder engagement process and establishment of the Nitra IN-HUB. IN-HUB Management guidelines were essential in tracking how the organisation of the IN-HUB and the decision-making process took shape and evolved during the project, especially since Nitra IN-HUB is a less formalized partnership, developed gradually and continued to evolve even after its initial launch during the co-design process. Periodical updating of the organisational chart provided by TSR proved to be a great tool to analyse different stages of the IN-HUB development, while the engagement diaries were a great tool to reflect on the process. During the co-deployment phase Nitra IN-HUB will use diaries to track the process not only by the LCAs, but also by selected stakeholders from the User Advisory Board.

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3.2. Training of LCAs in working methods

From March 23 to April 16 2021 transversal partners TSR, UREAD, DFC, ISIM and BOT organised a 5 day-long online training workshops for Local Community Activators selected to facilitate project tasks in four pilot cities. The programme of the training sessions was following:

- Understanding the transformation process aimed by IN-HABIT (presentation of the structure of the training, sharing needs and expectations, learning about tools for exploring the local context and impact evaluation methods and tools)
- Gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion (GDEI) approach (discussing specifically the Inclusive aspect of IHW, with the introduction of the GDEI approach, the strategy to outreach groups at risk of exclusion and a verification of the stakeholder map according to GDEI criteria.
- Communication and storytelling (general view on communication tasks and tools, starting from the INHABIT Communication Plan, an introduction to the important role of storytelling)
- From vision to co-design (dedicated to the co-creation of Visionary Integrated Solutions with the participation of citizens - especially groups at risk of exclusion, including the presentation of the I CAN method that will be applied in Co-design laboratories under the supervision of DFC partner)
- Managing the IN-HUB (management of the local IN-HUBS, including list of tasks and expected deliveries, toolkit including tools and templates for facilitating the engagement of citizens in the activities, an exercise of local action planning)

During the LCA training only one LCA employed by the HIDE partner was selected, due to temporary difficulties in hiring process at the SUA partner and inability to find a suitable candidate. However, 3 members of Nitra team completed the training, LCA employed by HIDE, local WP4 coordinator from SUA and another researcher from SUA, temporary responsible for LCA tasks. After the completion of the training, acquired tools, skills and knowledge were transferred to the rest of the team by those participating and to the second LCA selected by the SUA partner in August 2021.

3.3. Co-design of IHW indicators

The subjective indicators on socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles have been selected by means of a co-design process where the theoretical and empirical assumptions of the researchers have been integrated with the view of the local inhabitants and representatives of local organizations on the expected changes on people's health and wellbeing which may be, at least in part, attributable to the solutions envisaged in the 4 pilot cities.

The co-design started from the literature review and the theoretical conceptualization of inclusive health and wellbeing based on wellbeing studies, which has been integrated with the analysis of relevant assessment frameworks and metrics on health and wellbeing at European and international level, with specific regard to OECD – Better life initiative – Compendium of OECD well-being indicators 2011;

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EUROSTAT Final report of the expert group on quality of life indicators 2017 edition; UNDP-SDGs assessment indicators; WHO-QOL metrics on mental health; International Labour Organization indicators on labour inclusion; EKLIPSE indicators on NBS assessment. At the end of this phase, a first set of IHW Indicators has been selected. This set of indicators has been shared with the city partners (universities and cities) at month 2 and a feedback of their validity, measurability and specificity with respect to the urban context has been collected.

The second phase of the co-design process in Nitra took place in December 2020, when three workshops (two online and one in person) were run by SUA research group involving 12 inhabitants (3 males and 9 females). Among the participants, 6 of them identified themselves as members of groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion by ethnic origin and 2 of them by religion. Among the participants, 7 were members of local neighbourhood committees and NGOs, while 3 were representatives of local private companies.

The first discussion point of the workshop was about the most relevant aspects of health and well-being perceived by the participants. Secondly, the participants were asked about the expected changes in terms of health and wellbeing that may be produced by IN-HABIT VIS in Nitra in general as well as for the main project's target group in the city. The last discussion point was about the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on their health and wellbeing.

In addition to this, a consultation with the members of those NGOs representing some of the groups at risk of discrimination at the city level allowed to get a deeper insight on the perspective of those groups regarding their needs and expected changes on health and wellbeing. In Nitra, a total of 9 NGOs were consulted representing/working with: women; ethnic or national minorities; elderly; persons with disabilities; homeless, drugs addicted people.

The final list of IHW indicators specific to Nitra pilot that resulted from this process is provided in Annex 8.

3.4. Secondary data collection

Among the quantitative research actions within the proposed plan, transversal partner ISIM ran the analysis of secondary data (open data, administrative data and available statistics) with the help of the city partners SUA and NITRA. This activity will be carried twice (ex-ante and ex-post) during the project lifetime and it will be used for the analysis of the 4 city context with the twofold aim of (i) better interpretation of the IN-HABIT results and (ii) discounting external factors who may have contributed to the changes affecting inhabitants' IHW.

In order to support city partners in the collection of secondary data for the baseline study, ISIM and UREAD have provided SUA and NITRA with guidance and support by delivering:

- a list of indicators for IHW specifically designed for the collection of secondary data

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- written guidelines for local public authorities on how to collect secondary data, also considering GDEI data. For each dimension/indicator, the production of data disaggregated by age, gender, and - where available – other GDEI personal characteristics has been required
- organizing meetings and informative sessions to offer support and assistance to the city partners in case of need

IHW dimensions for secondary data collection included: demography, socio-economic well-being, attitudes and participation, poverty and income, housing, education, employment, crime, discrimination and violence, consumption, time use, health, health determinants, mobility and mental health.

Secondary data collection in Nitra was challenging from several perspectives. First, the residential neighbourhood, although a separate district of the city is not a separate administrative unit, so only very basic data regarding demographic characteristics are available. Second, the Nitra pilot also covers territory of the industrial park, City Park and other not formally demarcated areas thus it is impossible to gather secondary data because no official borders of the pilot area exist. Data for a number of indicators are only available on the district and some even on the regional level. Frequency of data gathering is also an issue, since some of the data came from population census administered only every 10 years, which makes it difficult to use for both ex-ante and ex-post evaluation. Additionally, some of the data was gathered from a one-off analyses commissioned by the NITRA partner with no plans for repeating them (e.g. analysis carried out as a part of Sustainable Mobility Plan preparation in 2018). For most of the data disaggregation based on GDEI characteristics is not available. As a result only a portion of the required secondary data for Nitra pilot is available on the city level. Availability, year of reference, source and level of disaggregation of required secondary data are indicated in Annex 9.

3.5. GDEI determinants of spatial and functional elements/or Gendered landscape

GDEI is a key aspect of the IN-HABIT project that brings an essential attention to the fair distribution of health and well-being to everybody, and in particular to the strategies to reduce the gap for those at major risk of exclusion. It questions the design of the urban space and its effects through men and women's different experiences and improves inclusivity across 3 pillars:

- Institutions: to mainstream gender and diversity in administrative processes.
- Lived experiences: understanding the extent to which the cities are lived differently by different social groups, and how to design an inclusive urban space for all.
- Health and wellbeing inequality: mapping the extent of inequality in health and wellbeing in the cities to understand how urban design affects these aspects.

At this stage, data required for the first pillar was gathered by partners SUA and NITRA and analysed by transversal partner UREAD. The objective of this pillar is to produce a comprehensive mapping of the institutional frameworks that supports decision-making at the city level. The mapping informs our

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understanding of the extent to which gender and diversity aspects have been taken into consideration in policy making at different levels, from political commitment to the possible implementation of action plans.

At the municipal office of City of Nitra out of total number of 272 employees, 187 are women, which represents 69%. However in decision-making bodies women are underrepresented by a wide margin. In local district assemblies out of 93 citizens and council members involved only 23 are women, making the participation rate of only 25%. On the city level, the most important decision making body is the city council, where out of total of 31 council members, only six are women, which makes only 19%.

The city does not have a separate GDEI focused policy, various topics are however covered by several policies and strategies. The Accessibility For All Strategy developed in 2019, does not mention gender based inclusion policies as such, but rather specific situations that can disproportionately affect women (e.g. accessibility while using stroller). Community Plan of Social Services focuses on groups such as elderly population, population with disabilities, families with children and persons at risk of social exclusion, but does not mention gender dimension specifically. The only policy document that recognises women as a defined target group is the “Strategy for dealing with risky behaviour with a focus on drugs and the elimination of domestic violence, violence against women and children in the city of Nitra”.

3.6. Survey, interviews and focus groups

The impact assessment of the city solutions on IHW are run in WP7 by partner ISIM in close collaboration with the local community activators and local research partners. The baseline study on IHW data gathering was conducted from September 2021 to October 2021. It consisted of:

- 1 city survey was administered, where 351 interviews were collected using online and paper distribution method
- 2 focus groups were organised with a total number of 9 participants (2 men, 7 women) with inclusion of representatives of elderly, young people, persons with physical disability and economic migrants, also Nitra specific special users group like cyclists
- 5 stories were collected with total number of 6 protagonists (3 men, 2 women and 1 non-binary) representing a couple of economic migrants working in the industrial park, 1 elderly man, the oldest volunteer at the Hidepark community and cultural centre, 1 man with physical disability, 1 elderly woman living in the residential area of Dražovce, and 1 young member of the LGBTQI community

Some of the key findings are:

- relatively higher self-reported perception of discrimination, listing social conflicts between Slovaks and immigrants as well as with the Roma community
- lower level of accessibility to culture and leisure opportunities, with mobility obstacles for elderly and lack of adequate cultural offer for young people and ethnic minorities and lack of inclusive cultural spaces

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- lower level of trust in local authorities, experience a low sense of safety at night and increased instances of vandalism
- immigrant workers experience a severe domestic isolation and social exclusion
- lower accessibility of local resources, especially cultural events, green areas to do sports and healthy food

The key findings of the IHW baseline survey are listed in Appendix 9 and illustrated in following charts while a detailed analysis of these results is presented in D7.3 Baseline study on IHW report elaborated by partner ISIM.

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Intervention Group — People living in Dražovce neighbourhood or frequenting one of the green areas along the cycle road connecting Dražovce with the old city centre.

Control Group — The rest of the inhabitants of Nitra

> SOCIAL WELL-BEING

> EQUALITY AND DISCRIMINATION

Participants from the intervention group reported higher perception of discrimination and inequality, in particular based on ethnicity and age.

> PERCEPTION OF SECURITY

Participants from the intervention group experience a lower sense of safety at night and greater fear of road accidents.

> SOCIAL INCLUSION

Participants from the intervention group experience a good sense of community, social engagement and change making attitude. On the other hand, they report low levels of civic engagement and trust in the institutions and the group of migrant workers suffers a condition of severe domestic isolation.

> SOCIAL COHESION

Participants from the intervention group experience **satisfaction with personal relationships and trust in others**, by reporting kindness and solidarity from neighbours.

Perceive **social conflicts** between Slovaks and migrants as well as with the Roma community.

> SPATIAL WELL-BEING

> ACCESSIBILITY OF RESOURCES IN THE NEIGHBOURHOOD

★ Participants from the control group report a better accessibility of local resources in the neighbourhood.

> SATISFACTION WITH THE NEIGHBOURHOOD AND URBAN GREEN AREAS

★ Participants from the intervention group report **lower satisfaction with the urban green areas** where they spend the majority of their free time.

> PHYSICAL HEALTH AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

> HEALTHY HABITS

- The habit of **consuming self-grown fruit and vegetables is widespread** among the inhabitants who attend the community center of Hydepark and could be extended to other social groups or city areas.
- Participants from the intervention group are **aware of benefits from urban nature** and perceive these benefits as potentially increasing in the next future.

> LEISURE AND FREE TIME

- People from the intervention group experience **healthy leisure practices** like walking in nature, cycling, attendance of parks and green areas, sports practice and community gardening. However, they perceive an **impoverishment of the quality of their free time in public spaces due to the Covid effects**.
- The practice of healthy leisure could be improved with respect to the group of local migrant workers.

> MENTAL HEALTH

People from the intervention group experience **comparable levels of psychological well-being and mental distress.**

> ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

People from the intervention group express concern with the **access to house and affordability of houses.**

Covid pandemic caused a decrease of the income in the tourist and cultural sector as well as higher job insecurity for migrant workers in the industrial district.

4. Co-design of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS): bottom-up participative process

4.1. Bottom-up methods and tools used

Figure 3 Co-design logic of Nitra pilot (process and milestones, involved stakeholders and methods applied)

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The chart in Figure 3 details all methods used in the co-design process of VIS in Nitra pilot, involvement of stakeholder groups as they were defined during IN-HUB establishment, along with specific stages when they were applied. Methodology was conceptualised based on resources provided by toolkit elaborated by transversal partner TSR, the knowledge and skills gained through LCA training, but adapted to the specificities of the local context and the nature of initially proposed VIS.

All of the methods mentioned are interconnected and feed into each other in such a way that would allow for a delivery of detailed innovative but also feasible solutions with synergic effects and sound plans for their co-deployment and co-management. Results of methods used in one stage of the co-design process are an input for the next stage. The final results of the process are VIS and ITP built gradually from the ground up, but also validated by stakeholders on several levels.

As specific VIS started to take shape, the initial IN-HUB members and “settings” expanded significantly, meaning the continuous stakeholder mapping and engagement process is an intrinsic part of the co-design as well.

Specific methods, their results and how they resulted in the final proposal for VIS in Nitra pilot are described in the next chapter.

4.2. Co-design workshops

The first co-design workshop with IN-HUB members was organized as a second session after the official IN-HUB launch on 1.8.2021. During the process participants were engaged in **association exercises** where they created **association chains**.

Each of the participants was handed and asked to indicate all of the locations in the pilot area that are either interesting, underutilized, need care and revitalisation, unsafe, have potential to be used in a different way, or are a point where different target groups are concentrated. Overall participants identified 13 locations. In the second step they were asked to propose types of activities that either them or any of the target groups could do/would be interested in at that locality and specify types of users that would attract. Finally, after the discussion participants proposed types of elements (proto-VIS) that are needed for those activities to be possible at specific localities.

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Figure 4 Association exercises with Nitra IN-HUB

Total number of 10 association chains were developed by the participants and recorded. 13 locations in the pilot area were identified, the original user and target groups were better defined and elements and activities became a sort of proto-VIS, hard and soft respectively.

Locality	Activity	User	Element
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Underpass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •street art, paintings, exhibition, sculptures, small musical performances, •underpass lighting for safety •rest during riding a bike •greening 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •NR residents, visitors, students, artists •everyone •cyclists •humans and insects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •art under the bridge, graffiti wall •lamps •rain protection, relax zone with mobiliary •green roof structure

Figure 5 Example of the association chain

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Figure 6 Partial results from the association exercises

Second co-design workshop took place on 22. August 2021 with members of the Core IN-HUB, as well as additional representatives of target groups. Workshop took place in the pilot area as an **interactive transect walkthrough** of the corridor.

Prior to the workshop, results of the previous workshop and suggestions from IN-HUB members (a couple of association exercises were conducted individually with IN-HUB members that could not participate) were compiled, analysed and synthesized by LCAs, local WP4 coordinator and co-design facilitator into initial proposals for solutions. Transects of identified zones and locations of interest were created.

All participants were handed a map, transect with a table and a diary to record the process, discussions and their own comments. The workshop was run by LCAs and co-design facilitator. Most of the 13 locations identified during the prior workshop were visited, inspected, existing and planned interventions of other initiatives, projects and entities relevant to the areas were discussed, along with ownership and jurisdiction issues. Participants described, discussed and recorded safety and accessibility issues as well as their emotions and experiences related to the locations. Finally, proposed activities and elements to be co-designed and co-deployed there as VIS were discussed in terms of their feasibility.

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Figure 7 Interactive transect walk through the pilot area with Nitra IN-HUB

Transekt:						
Lokalita:	ZEWOVER	UDEPARA	TOPOLOVA MIEŠTRIZOBA	Dobrotka	Právnelyj park	DRAZOVICE
Aktivita:	lybárenie ubúšťie hry (futbal...)	Hry pred bldy	šport šport		šport	HRISKO byčubové športy
Užívatelia:	ľudia z mesta okolo	ľudia z mesta okolo	Všetci	človek Príjemný	športovníci Príjemný	okolo mesta Dražovic
Elementy:	môta grúdy	HRISKO Prehľad puky	športy	okolo športu	športy	okolo mesta športy
Existujúce a plánované intervencie v rámci iných iniciatív:		HP Lvgový			?	nie sú v úvahu
Bezpečnosť:	bezdomoci	neúhľad športu	športy športy so stavom a nebezpečnosť		Dobrá	nie úplne okolo športu
Prístupnosť:	autóm okolo	autóm okolo	okolo okolo okolo	okolo		Dobrá
Pochybnosti:	Príjemný okolo okolo		Príjemný okolo okolo okolo	okolo okolo okolo	okolo okolo okolo	okolo okolo okolo

Figure 8 Partial results from interactive transect walk

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Based on the inputs from IN-HUB members during the transect walk, the initial association chains were updated by partners SUA, HIDE and NITRA and initial proposal for hard and soft VIS to be co-deployed in Nitra pilot was compiled.

During the initial part of the next stage (September – November 2021) some of the tasks that were part of the top-down process were of interest to the co-design of specific VIS as well, namely the **5 stories** collected and **2 focus groups** organised as a part of IHW baseline analysis in cooperation with transversal partner ISIM.

During the first stages of the co-design process representatives of one major vulnerable group were absent. Members of local Roma community did not attend the workshops, although bilateral communication with relevant institutional stakeholders was already initiated. This is why project partner NITRA together with NGO Post Bellum SK⁷ organised on 9th September 2021 a day-long interactive workshop on the 80th anniversary of adoption of the Jewish Code⁸ for Roma schoolchildren aged 12-15 from all neighbourhoods of the city. During this workshop partners SUA and HIDE conducted a **focus group exploring topics of segregation**, participation in community and cultural activities, leisure and free time use and the role of their community in Nitra's social fabric. From participants and their teachers, we found that they usually visit cultural and community venues only as a school activity but are “mostly bored there”. They frequent and feel happiest in shopping centres, nightclubs, by the Nitra River. Findings stemming from this focus group informed our next stakeholder engagement strategy – more intensive involvement of schools with higher attendance by Roma children, not only as members of the IN-HUB, but also as direct partners on several planned VIS.

Subsequent co-design process during the September to November 2021 stage ran on several lanes:

- IN-HABIT Co-design Atelier was offered as an elective course by SUA partner
- Discussions and negotiations with group of affiliated stakeholders regarding specific VIS
- Validation of specific VIS with corresponding members of Institutional Support and Oversight group

IN-HABIT Co-design Atelier was facilitated by experts in design and architecture, green infrastructure planning, landscape ecology and dendrology. 10 master students of Landscape Architecture took part in the Atelier. They were given results from the first stage of the co-design process and compiled proposals for VIS and based on those they conducted field research and study in the pilot area. Field analyses consisted of: accessibility analysis, analysis of existing infrastructure and safety, analysis of adjacent areas, space openness and outlook analysis, noise pollution analysis, emotional mapping of the space and territory potential analysis. Selected results and outputs from the process are illustrated in Annex 11.

⁷ <https://www.postbellum.sk/english/>

⁸ The so-called Jewish Code was adopted by the wartime Slovak state in 1941, which limited the fundamental rights of Jews and rendered them second-class citizens.

Figure 9 Co-design process in the IN-HABIT Co-design Atelier

Simultaneously project partners ran numerous **bilateral negotiations** with relevant institutional members of User Advisory Board, affiliated stakeholders relevant to specific VIS (either due to ownership or jurisdiction relations, experts or as potential partners in co-deployment and co-management). During this stage, the group of affiliated stakeholders expanded significantly, while some became regular members of the Core IN-HUB as well, opting to increase their participation intensity.

Bilateral negotiations regarding VIS were also conducted with relevant policy representatives (members of Institutional Support and Oversight group) to validate specific VIS. The validation entailed **checking compliance** with city-wide policies, strategic documents and existing or planned interventions and projects. VIS we either checked against priorities, specific objectives or action plans in case of documents like the community plan or the cultural strategy, or against technical requirements of documents like public space design manual, accessibility strategy or general urban greenery plan. All relevant policies and strategic documents that were cross-checked with planned VIS are listed in table 5.

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Table 5 Cross-compliance check with relevant policies and strategic documents

Strategic document	Links
Accessibility For All Strategy	https://www.nitra.sk/zobraz/sekcii/narodne-projekty-10439
III. Community plan of social services of the city of Nitra for 2021 - 2025	https://www.nitra.sk/zobraz/obsah/32473
Situational analysis of migration and possibilities of integration of foreigners in the city of Nitra	https://comin.sk/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Situa%c4%8dn%c3%a1-anal%c3%bdza-CVEK.pdf
NK31 - Strategy for the Development of Culture and the Creative Industry 2021 - 2031	https://www.nitra.sk/zobraz/obsah/33344
Sustainable Mobility Plan	https://www.nitra.sk/zobraz/sekcii/pum-10441
Bicycle transport concept in the city of Nitra	https://docplayer.org/35748914-Koncepcia-cyklickej-dopravy-v-meste-nitra.html
Public Space Design Manual: Nitra Visible	http://uzemnyplan.nitra.sk/nitra-viditelna/
Urban Plan of the City of Nitra	http://uzemnyplan.nitra.sk/platny-uzemny-plan/ http://uzemnyplan.nitra.sk/vizia/
Low-carbon strategy of the city of Nitra for 2021 - 2040	https://www.nitra.sk/zobraz/sekcii/nizkouglikov-a-strategia-pre-mesto-nitra-10483
General urban greenery plan for the City of Nitra	In development
The program of economic and social development of the City of Nitra for 2015-2023, Action Plan 2020-2021	https://www.nitra.sk/zobraz/obsah/18663 https://www.nitra.sk/zobraz/obsah/32868
Integrated territorial strategy of the urban functional area of the city of Nitra for 2022 - 2027 with an outlook until 2030	In development, currently in SEA stage (Strategic Environmental Assessment)

Next day-long **co-design validation workshop** was held on 22nd November 2021 with Nitra IN-HUB. Initial plan for VIS was re-evaluated based on the discussions and negotiations with affiliated stakeholders and institutional stakeholders in terms of their feasibility. During the workshop updated plan was presented to the members of the IN-HUB and detailed explanations and justification were given why some of the proposed solutions were either updated or left out based on the field research and analysis, feasibility check and validation process. Final plan for VIS was subsequently revised with the IN-HUB in an adapted **World Café** format where stakeholders from different advisory groups were divided into 4 moderated groups (based on 4 zones of the pilot area) in order to develop proposed VIS in terms of combining social and community innovations, art and cultural innovations, sport, alternative mobility modes, education, NBS and digital and technical innovations into solutions with synergic effects on IHW dimensions of focus in given zones of the pilot area.

Second part of the co-design workshop was a **moderated discussion** on functions, reversibility, safety and accessibility features as well as self-service feature from GDEI and Nitra specific target groups' perspective

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of each of the proposed elements of VIS. Third part of the workshop was dedicated to moderated discussion on co-deployment and co-management process for each proposed VIS.

Figure 10 Validation co-design workshop with IN-HUB Nitra

Results of the workshop was the final validation of proposed VIS, their functionalities and material, accessibility and use requirements.

During December 2021 – January 2022, these were presented to and analysed by **IN-HABIT Co-design Atelier**. Landscape Architecture students, together with experts from SUA elaborated several final proposals for several VIS.

Annex 12 shows final result of the co-design process for location “Beavers Yard” in the City Park (Location 2.3, Solutions 2.3.1, 2.3.2, 2.3.3 listed in Chapter 5.2). Students and experts proposed several elements of VIS (the promenade, pier and other mobiliary elements, houses for cats etc.) based on the requirements proposed by IN-HUB at the validation workshop. They analysed material availability and prices, elaborated technical specifications and visualisation of final solutions and proposed an indicative budget. As part of this process during winter break in December and January a **literary and art contest** was organized for schoolchildren in Elementary school Dražovce and Elementary school Tulipánová. Proposal and technical documentation illustrated in Annex 12 is not final, it will still be subjected to validation on all three levels of the IN-HUB prior to co-deployment.

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Due to the increase of COVID cases and subsequent restrictions on meetings, but also due to the necessity to work on outdoor open spaces in colder winter months, partners developed an **online co-design tool using Kuula⁹ software** to be used in the co-design process. Several least accessible localities in the pilot area were 3D scanned and mapped using a drone and virtual tours of those locations were created. Users of the tool can model specific interventions from the comfort of their home, but also together during the co-design workshops. In the 3D space, they can work with prepared gif and png drawings of the co-designed elements, use symbols, marks, text fields, emoticons, differentiate their inputs in colour. The interface is user-friendly, and video guide was prepared and shared by the project partners. In reality however, this tool did not get used substantially and users rather choose to compile their suggestions and send them to either another more tech savvy IN-HUB member or a researcher to be uploaded by them. Virtual tour of the location “Beavers Yard” for which the final results of the co-design process were shown in Annex 12 can be found here: <https://kuula.co/post/NXfTG/collection/7qnyG>.

Figure 11 Use of online tool Kuula in the co-design process and partial results

4.3. Design for Change (DFC) workshops to promote mindset change

The I CAN LAB Mindset Change workshop led by the transversal partner DFC was held in Nitra on 12th and 13th of November 2021. During the 12-hour long workshop total of 7 educators were trained in the Design for Change methodology. Its objective was to give the tools to educators to help the community (women, children, young people, people with disabilities...) become the primary actors and agents of change in their communities and environment.

⁹ <https://kuula.co/>

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The structure of the workshop was organized in three blocks, all with the active participation of educators:

- Block 1: The aim is to start a positive integration between the participants. Explanation of the origin and basics of the methodology, providing of several examples.
- Block 2: The goal is to go through 5 steps of the methodology: Feel, Imagine, Do, Evaluate (Evaluation+Evolution) and Share. Participants form a relationship with the methodology and get involved in the process through direct experimentation on real situations.
- Block 3: Participants had the opportunity to try out the role of facilitator and apply what they have learned. Subsequently they asked questions to the experts present.

Invitations and registration form for the workshop were distributed through the IN-HUB, as well as other institutional networks where educators are members. The Department of Education in the city administration sent out the invitation to all the schools under their jurisdiction. Due to the increasing number of COVID cases and placement of certain restriction on meeting for employees in the school system, mostly educators from NGOs and private sector were involved, since most of the educators working in the public sector had to cancel shortly prior to the date of the workshop.

Key feature of the mindset change workshop in Nitra, was that it was held in the local language as partner DFC managed to find a Slovak speaking facilitator. From those participating and trained in the methodology, the response was very positive. One of the participating educator expressed an interest to be trained in the methodology as a facilitator. Couple of others educators expressed their intent to use the methodology in their respective educational practice.

Figure 12 DFC workshop in Nitra

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4.4 Co-design process in numbers

Date	Activity	Participants
1 st August 2021	1 st co-design workshop – associations exercises	11 members of Core IN-HUB group (institutional and individual)
22 nd August 2021	Interactive transect walk of the corridor	12 members of Core IN-HUB group (institutional and individual)
9 th September 2021	Workshop and focus group with Roma schoolchildren	16 present for the workshop, 9 focus group participants
September – October 2021	Baseline study on IHW – partially informed the co-design process	2 focus groups (9 participants), 5 stories and 351 interviews
September – November 2021 November 2021 – January 2022	IN-HABIT Co-design Atelier	Field analysis with 10 Landscape architecture students and 3 experts
22 nd November 2021	Validation co-design workshop, 4 worldcafé tables and moderated discussion	13 Core IN-HUB group members (institutional and individual)
September – February 2021	Individual consultations with policy representatives (cross-compliance with relevant strategic documents) and with affiliated stakeholders regarding co-deployment and co-management of VIS	50+ meetings with 14 policy representatives for local, regional and national level 60+ meetings and consultations with affiliated stakeholders' group regarding specific VIS
December 2021 – January 2022	Literary and art contest	2 elementary schools (20+ students)

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5. City-specific VIS to boost IHW

5.1.Planned hard and soft solutions

General objective of Nitra pilot was to improve healthy lifestyles, social inclusion of migrants, social cohesion and relational wellbeing among local inhabitants of Dražovce neighbourhood and with the rest of the city by creating a Reversible Multifunctional Open-source Urban Landscape along the 8 km cycle road. The initial plans envisaged for visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) in Nitra by all three project partners included:

- reversible co-deployed Multifunctional Open-source Urban Landscape (REMOULD) along the 8 km-long cycle road, with multifunctional recreational zones, services (bicycle stands, sanitary facilities), sports, playgrounds and leisure facilities;
- community kitchen, community and experimental garden and a DIY café in Hidepark, to deliver public crafts workshop, bike-sharing services with repair shop and service station;
- training courses for urban gardeners and therapy gardening activities;
- digital services provided throughout the INHABIT-APP to support outdoor sports activities and participation to socialization, cultural and training/employment initiatives.
- culinary events, vocational training and educational activities, with the involvement of children, elderly and other vulnerable groups;
- cultural initiatives and art performances, using intercultural dialogue as a means for integration.

5.2.Co-designed VIS

Rather than organising different VIS thematically around different types of innovative and visionary solutions, during the first co-design workshop, IN-HUB members decided that they should rather be organised around demarcation of the pilot area into 4 zones (due to its size) and then around identified locations that were targeted. This approach pushed for better combination of different innovative and visionary elements to allow for a greater synergic effect of the final solutions on the relevant dimensions of the IHW. The table below provides a complete list of the co-designed solutions, while their spatial distribution is illustrated in Annex 13. Annex 14 details co-designed hard VIS in Nitra pilot, their description, technical, qualitative and quantitative requirements, target groups and intended users as well as stakeholders involved.

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Table 6 Final list of co-designed hard VIS

Zone	Location		Solutions	
Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street	1.1	Near Zelokvet	1.1.1	Picnic Meadow
	1.2	River bank	1.2.1	Replacement planting of the tree alley: 45-50 trees
			1.2.2	Lighting
	1.3	Hidepark	1.3.1	Building of sewerage and drinking water supply, sanitary container
			1.3.2	Revitalization and expansion of community garden
			1.3.3	Rowboat rental on the Nitra River
			1.3.4	Food booth - community kitchen
			1.3.5	DIY Café - community workshop
			1.3.6	Community bike-sharing station and service
			1.3.7	Inclusive playground for children
1.4	Bridge at Vodna street	1.4.1	Landmark for REMOULD corridor	
Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge	2.1	Elementary school Tulipánova	2.1.1	Educational therapeutic garden
	2.2	Nitra River surface	2.2.1	Artistic object on the surface on abandoned concrete structures
			2.2.2	Floating flower beds - cRAFTS
	2.3	City Park - Beaver's Yard	2.3.1	Pier and mobiliary
			2.3.2	Green interventions
			2.3.3	Innovative educational elements
	2.4	City park	2.3.4	Lighting
			2.4.1	Bicycles for people with disabilities
			2.4.2	Public mobile sauna
	2.4.3	Installation of elements from poplar trunks		
Park bridge – Underpass – Industrial park	3.1	West Slovak Water Company	3.1.1	Waterworks Garden
	3.2	Swamp Biotop	3.2.1	Restoration and conservation of the natural vegetation system in the swamp habitat
			3.2.2	Lighting
	3.3	Dobrotka Stream Bank	3.3.1	Tree planting
	3.4	Underpass	3.4.1	Small architecture and art object with the function of a skateboard and pump track
			3.4.2	Lighting
3.5	Dobrotka Stream Bank	3.5.1	Mobiliary for leisure along the cycle path	

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	3.6	Parking lot - Industrial park	3.6.1	Chill and SmallTalk zone
	3.7	Industrial park	3.7.1	Tree planting - Industrial park
Dražovce Residential Area	4.1	Entry to Dražovce	4.1.1	Public picnic zone
			4.1.2	Lighting
	4.2	Cultural centre and adjacent areas	4.2.1	Inclusive playground
			4.2.2	Garden with therapeutic elements
			4.2.3	Seating mobiliary
			4.2.4	Mobile marketplace "Dražovisko"
	4.3	Elementary school Dražovce	4.3.1	Therapeutic and educational garden
			4.3.2	Multifunctional mobiliary
			4.3.3	Educational Playground
			4.3.4	Lighting

Co-designed soft and cross-sectional solutions include establishment of online IN-HUB platform, Online Living Library, activities aimed at skill development and NBS and craft based entrepreneurship promotion, substantial portfolio of educational activities, workshops and courses, community events for general public and special dramaturgy for underused community centre in Dražovce, sport and healthy lifestyle events, art events and public space interventions, establishing platform for supporting local leaders and fundraising and accompanying publication activity. These are all detailed in Annex 15, along with plans for their co-deployment and co-management. Soft activities were designed to be complimentary to hard VIS, to ease their co-deployment process and subsequent co-management during and after the end of the project.

Each hard VIS has a designated timeline for co-deployment, business models proposals described in co-deployment and co-management plans, all detailed on pages 97 – 122. Table 6.1 on the next page additionally provides photodocumentation on the locations where hard solutions are to be deployed, along with the links to IHW subdimensions of expected changes and impacts. We distinguish between direct connections of proposed VIS to expected dimensions of impacts, but also indirect expected contributions. The indirect impacts capture the effect of hard VIS co-deployment mostly in conjunction with related soft activities, or they are brought about by specific mode of co-deployment. For example although hard solutions tied to provision of new urban green areas (e.g. tree planting, urban meadow establishment), we expect to involve local population and specific disadvantaged groups in the process of co-deployment and co-management through volunteer work with associated training, thus increasing their skill level as well.

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Table 6.1 Co-designed hard solutions to be deployed in the pilot area divided into four zones

LOCATIONS		VIS		LINKS TO IHW SUBDIMENSIONS - direct	LINKS TO IHW SUBDIMENSIONS - indirect
<p>1.1 Near Zelokvet</p>	1.1.1	Picnic Meadow	Spatial Wellbeing, Equality, Leisure/free time	Social cohesion	
		1.2.1	Replacement planting of the tree alley: 45-50 trees	Spatial Wellbeing	Leisure/free time, Employability, Job and Skills satisfaction
		1.2.2	Lighting	Perception of security	Spatial Wellbeing
		1.3.1	Building of sewerage and drinking water supply, sanitary container	Spatial Wellbeing	Sports facilities, Cultural consumption and production
		1.3.2	Revitalization and expansion of community garden	Spatial Wellbeing, Leisure/free time, Determinants of health	Social cohesion, Social inclusion, Job and Skills satisfaction, Psychological wellbeing
		1.3.3	Rowboat rental on the Nitra River	Sports facilities, Physical health status, Determinants of health	Spatial Wellbeing
		1.3.4	Food booth - community kitchen	Leisure/free time, Determinants of health	Social cohesion, Social inclusion, Cultural consumption and production
		1.3.5	DIY Café - community workshop	Leisure/free time, Employability, Job and Skills satisfaction	Social cohesion, Social inclusion
		1.3.6	Community bike-sharing station and service	Determinants of health, Sports facilities, Leisure/free time, Physical health status	Spatial Wellbeing
		1.3.7	Inclusive playground for children	Sports facilities, Physical health status, Equality, Leisure/free time	Social cohesion
<p>1.2 River bank</p>	1.4.1	Landmark for REMOULD corridor	Spatial Wellbeing, Leisure/free time	Equality	
<p>1.4 Bridge at Vodná Street</p>					

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<p>2.1 Elementary school Tulipanova</p>	2.1.1	Educational therapeutic garden	Determinants of health, Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Psychological wellbeing, Equality	
		2.2.1	Artistic object on river	Cultural consumption and production	Leisure/free time
<p>2.2 Nitra River</p>	2.2.2	Floating flower beds - cRAFTS	Spatial Wellbeing, Determinants of health		
		2.3.1	Pier and mobiliary	Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Social cohesion
<p>3.1 Slovak Water C.</p>	2.3.2	Green interventions	Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing		
		2.3.3	Innovative educational elements	Cultural consumption and production, Leisure/free time	
		2.3.4	Lighting	Perception of security	Spatial Wellbeing
		2.4.1	Bicycles for people with disabilities	Equality, Determinants of health, Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Discrimination
		2.4.2	Public mobile sauna	Sports facilities, Determinants of health, Physical health status	Social cohesion
		2.4.3	Installation of elements from poplar trunks	Cultural consumption and production, Leisure/free time	Social inclusion
		3.1.1	Waterworks Garden	Cultural consumption and production, Leisure/free time	
		3.2.1	Restoration and conservation of the natural vegetation system	Spatial Wellbeing, Leisure/free time	
		3.2.2	Lighting	Perception of security	Spatial Wellbeing
		<p>3.2 Swamp biotope</p>	3.3.1	Tree planting	
3.4.1	Small architecture and art object with the function of a skateboard and pump track			Cultural consumption and production, Leisure/free time, Sports facilities	Social cohesion
<p>3.3 Dobrotka stream</p>	3.4.2	Lighting	Perception of security	Spatial Wellbeing	
		3.5.1	Mobiliary for leisure along the cycle path	Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Equality
		3.6.1	Chill and SmallTalk zone	Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Social cohesion
		3.7.1	Tree planting - Industrial park	Spatial Wellbeing	Leisure/free time, Employability, Job and Skills satisfaction

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<p>4.1 Entry to Dražovce</p>	4.1.1	Public picnic zone	Spatial Wellbeing, Equality, Leisure/free time, Determinants of health, Physical health status	Social cohesion	
		4.1.2	Lighting	Perception of security	Spatial Wellbeing
<p>4.2 Cultural centre</p>		4.2.1	Inclusive playground	Sports facilities, Physical health status, Equality, Leisure/free time	Social cohesion
		4.2.2	Garden with therapeutic elements	Determinants of health, Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Psychological wellbeing, Equality
		4.2.3	Seating mobiliary	Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Equality
		4.2.4	Mobile marketplace "Dražovisko"	Cultural consumption and production, Financial situation	Social cohesion
		4.3.1	Therapeutic and educational garden	Determinants of health, Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Psychological wellbeing, Equality
		4.3.2	Multifunctional mobiliary	Leisure/free time, Spatial Wellbeing	Equality
		4.3.3	Educational Playground	Sports facilities, Physical health status, Equality, Leisure/free time	Social cohesion
		4.3.4	Lighting	Perception of security	Spatial Wellbeing

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Timeline plan for soft VIS co-deployment for year 2022

Timeline above provides detailed calendar of soft activities co-deployment for current year. More details on these activities are provided on pages 123 – 129. Most are to be co-deployed in cooperation with various stakeholders, mostly members of the IN-HUB core group and affiliated stakeholders.

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5.3. Co-deployment and co-management of VIS

Plans for co-deployment and co-management processes were also a part of the co-design processes. Initial plans were discussed with IN-HUB during the validation co-design workshop on 22nd November 2021 and subsequently discussed, negotiated and for some even contracted during bilateral meetings with IN-HUB members and other relevant stakeholders throughout December 2021 – February 2022 co-design stage. This resulted in detailed plans for the co-deployment and co-management of majority of planned both hard and soft VIS as detailed in Annexes 14 and 15. For co-deployment of each solution detailed timeline is provided and partners and stakeholders involved are indicated. Co-deployment procedures will take form of bilateral cooperation agreements, inviting experts to co-organise workshops and events, sharing resources, artist residencies, open calls and public competitions etc.)

During formulation of the plans for co-deployment and co-management, principles of polycentric governance and PPPPs were always taken into account. In almost all of the solutions to be deployed, IN-HUB members are to be actively involved. Public procurement procedures will explore options of **social procurement methods** that are in accordance with Slovak legislation. Additionally for co-deployment of several hard VIS resources of local stakeholders are planned to be used as an **in-kind contribution**. The good example is the cooperation agreed with ADOREAL, llc a company that will provide all of the material (amounting to approximately 13,000€) for the construction and equipment of rowboat rental and building of the access to the river surface that will be managed by the IN-HABIT project partners, while for the company it's a form of promoting their products.

The **platform for support and development of local leaders and fundraising** will also be a very good tool during the co-deployment and co-management stage. This solution actually came out of a problem with budgetary restrictions that partners faced. Increase of prices of building and other materials due to COVID compared to 2018, when proposed solutions were initially budgeted and relatively low budget for VIS, compared to spatial scope of the pilot, meant that the needs of the communities and stakeholders and planned solutions exceeded the budget significantly. Rather than prioritizing certain needs, target groups and locations, partners decided to consider all of the VIS that were developed by the IN-HUB in the co-design process. To meet the budgetary requirements local project coordinator and LCA HIDE will provide training and assistance to local stakeholders (individual and NGOs) who express their interest to participate in the project with aim to help them obtain additional funding for VIS that are part of the Inclusive Transformation Plan from alternative sources (e.g. Slovak Art Support Fund, I'm Changing My City grant scheme, scholarships for residencies etc.). Other solutions include linking certain VIS to complimentary project of involved stakeholders etc. (e.g. Urbact OnStage project targeting schools with Roma majority).

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Figure 13 Interactive workshop for Dražovce elementary school children at Hidepark

Examples of some of the already co-deployed solutions include testing of planned soft solutions: **Interactive workshop with children of Elementary school Dražovce** (all were from local Roma families) on establishing a meadow, planting a tree, with educational dendrological walk, creating and gathering materials for herbarium. Workshop was organized on 22nd October 2021 at the Hidepark location in the pilot area and was co-deployed by partner SUA and HIDE, Botanical Garden and NGO Cuketa (member of the IN-HUB).

Second intervention that is currently in co-deployment phase are two linked solutions: the 1.2.1 Replacement planting of the tree alley on the Nitra river bank and 2.4.3 Installation of elements from poplar trunks in the City Park. Both are in co-deployment with partner Slovak Waterways Management Company, SUA, NITRA, Botanical Garden and in the future several other local stakeholders. Former iconic tree alley along the Nitra River was cut down in fall 2021 by the Slovak Waterways Management Company. The felling of 180 monumental black poplar trees, negatively impacted the general public of the city, with even petitions being initiated against it. IN-HABIT Nitra team established an agreement with the Waterways that they will let IN-HUB to revitalize and replant the part of the river bank where a lot of the solutions are planned. In return, Waterways provided a 10 tree trunks from poplar trees that were cut down near the City Park. These tree fragments will be re-introduced into the area where they were cut down as small art and mobiliary elements that will be designed by local artists and architects.

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Figure 14 Progress on VIS 1.2.1 and 2.4.3 co-deployment

6. Emerging lessons and recommendations

6.1. Challenges and achievements in the organization and development of the IN-HUB and PPPs schemes

Stakeholder mapping and engagement and establishing IN-HUB was not a substantial challenge for Nitra pilot. It is mostly due to the fact that we had a strong partner in HIDE with vast institutional and personal contact and partner network and experience in participative approaches in implementation of development initiatives. Another positive factor was that for Nitra stakeholder mapping and engagement starter as early as 2018 when the project proposal was being prepared.

More challenging, however, was maintaining that same level of engagement and involvement of identified stakeholders. We experienced a loss of interest among some of the IN-HUB members during the first 18 months of project implementation. Due to the time length of certain tasks and procedures of both stakeholder and community engagement and co-design process, certain IN-HUB members choose to leave the project. Some of their attitudes were *"I just don't understand why it takes so long to build a couple of benches"*. Some loose interest when dealing with topics that are not of their primary interest.

Conflicts of opinions and approaches of IN-HUB members were sometimes evident as well. Possible different views on certain issues and importance and feasibility of solutions are natural and are exacerbated by the fact that IN-HUB is an open and growing partnership and there is a possibility of conflicts of opinions between "old" and "new" members. Project partners, especially LCAs are responsible and crucial for

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stakeholder engagement process and subsequent expanding of IN-HUB. New members are always informed about the current state and membership in the IN-HUB, work already done and results obtained prior to decision about joining. Engagement process and seeking new partners to be included in the co-design, co-deployment and co-management of VIS are discussed with the IN-HUB. In case there is an important stakeholder that wants to take part in the project but for some reason (e.g. social anxiety) does not want to participate in the IN-HUB activities, the LCAs and co-design workshops leaders/facilitators consult with them individually.

Another issue for Nitra's IN-HUB was setting up the decision making processes. Due to the relatively large territorial scope of Nitra pilot as well as it containing vastly different neighbourhoods with different functional use (residential area, industrial park, recreational and cultural areas), that does not have a clear spatial demarcation and its borders are rather fuzzy, formalizing and institutionalizing especially decision making procedures within the Nitra IN-HUB is rather difficult. This is of utmost importance especially when decision about budget allocation for VIS among different thematic topics and its spatial distribution. Setting up a voting based procedure is virtually impossible, because there is not a clear way on how to distribute number of votes, especially among stakeholders from different localities within the pilot area. This is why discussions and final decision about these issues needs to be based on seeking consensus among all stakeholders rather than any sort of voting procedure. This approach, however, is less transparent because it's more difficult to monitor and report and creates higher transaction cost and is more time consuming. Due to the unfeasibility of setting up a voting based decision making processes, it is very important to build and maintain frequent two-way communication channel within different working groups and individual stakeholder in the IN-HUB. Crucial in this process are the two LCAs, especially the LCA HIDE who serves as a facilitator to the IN-HUB.

6.2. Challenges and achievements in combining bottom-up and top-down co-design, mindset change, and social innovations

There are no significant challenges identified in combining top-down (transversal partners) level and bottom-up (Nitra pilot) level methods and approaches. They complemented and fed into each other, especially methods used in the IHW baseline analysis with transversal partner ISIM. Stories collected during the storytelling activities and focus groups organised were a contributing input not only for setting up the baseline for defined IHW dimensions, but also for the co-design process of specific VIS. The only limiting factor was and continues to be the language barrier. Not all Nitra team members and LCAs speak fluent English so communication was slow at certain points. This barrier is even more evident with tasks conducted by transversal partners with local stakeholders and target groups, for example during the mindset change workshops. The solution that transversal partner DFC employed was hiring Slovak speaking facilitator to conduct the workshop in Nitra. Better synergic effects between top-down and bottom-up co-design process were also hindered by the Covid-19 pandemic related restrictions which made site visits by transversal partners in Nitra unfeasible.

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6.3.Challenges and achievements in ensuring the GDEI perspective

During the first 18 months, partners from Nitra experienced difficulties involving certain vulnerable groups. Roma community and migrant community were especially difficult to reach. This was determined by the fact, that unlike other target and vulnerable groups, these two communities do not have either formal institutionalised or informal representation. Roma community in Dražovce district lacks even emerging local leaders that could serve as observes and contact points in the IN-HUB and with the project partners and migrant community working in the industrial park does not socialize even among themselves. During the IN-HUB establishment and co-design process, project partners involved and worked with institutions/organisations that these groups frequent or communicate with. Roma community was involved mostly through top-down approach - via regional representative of Plenipotentiary of Slovak Republic for Roma minority (member of the community himself) and Elementary school Dražovce director and teachers, which is almost strictly Roma school (due to gradual segregation) attended by the children from local Roma community.

In the future, along with children, their families will be engaged during parent-teacher conferences organised by the school and other activities organised by the IN-HABIT partners on the school grounds using the solutions co-deployed there. Migrant community was involved directly through 4 representatives, through communication with their employers and COMIN - Community centre for work and knowledge mobility. In the future, to involve more representatives of wider range of migrant communities, NGO Mareena - a member of IN-HUB will use our co-designed and co-deployed solutions to carry out one-off Language Café events and longer Slovak language courses that are very sought after among these communities.

Another issue we encountered is the safe involvement of certain vulnerable groups and protecting their privacy. Choosing the right balance between integration, inclusion, joint decision making and ensuring the safety and privacy of certain groups (especially LGBTQI, Roma minority and economic migrants) poses a risk. Their direct involvement in IN-HUB activities is problematic due to language barriers (for economic migrants) and fear of speaking up and identifying as a member of certain groups (for LGBTQI people). Thus, target groups who do not feel safe to be actively involved in the discussion or have trouble communicating in local language were involved individually to ensure their comfort, safety and privacy (mostly through individual face-to-face meetings with Nitra project team members who they feel safe around and who speak their language).

6.4. Assessment of and reflection on the Toolkit: methods and tools used in the co-design, co-deployment, and co-management of VIS

Toolkit provided by transversal partners along with the training of LCAs was an excellent starting point for developing specific methods that were used in the co-design process in Nitra pilot, tailored to both specific requirements given our target groups, relatively large scope of the pilot area (required use of different approaches for different solutions) and planned VIS themselves.

Issues encountered during the co-design process include:

- Sometimes different parts of the IN-HUB behaved like "ships in the night". Two parts of Nitra IN-HUB do not communicate regularly, namely the stakeholder group in IN-HUB Core and representatives of Institutional Support and Oversight group. This is caused mostly by the fact that the Core group usually meets during off hours or even on weekends because most of the stakeholder representatives are NGO members and individual members who have "day jobs"¹⁰. On the other hand the latter groups in mostly comprised of representatives of public entities and policy representatives with vested interests and jurisdiction either within different thematic topics or different localities within pilot areas and their involvement is a part of their daily job. Parallel projects within the city and pilot area were found to be developed by some of the public sector and NGO members of the IN-HUB that do not communicate frequently.
- Although the pilot area is considered a public space and is freely accessible and used by the public, this is not always reflected by the ownership relations. Some of the localities where planned VIS are to be deployed are owned by different stakeholders (e.g. the Slovak Water Management Company, the church etc.)
- The problem of explaining the project to certain target groups both in terms of scope and method of implementation.
- Managing expectations - potential members sometimes voiced unrealistic requirements, for example for interventions where we do not have the competence to intervene.
- Some members of the IN-HUB decided to leave the project because the process seemed lengthy and for some it doesn't seem beneficial, because the basic services and amenities are not provided and they felt that issues above the standard are being addressed without basic standard of living being provided first. Some were of an opinion that the process requires too much commitment versus benefits for people involved.

¹⁰ NGO sector in Nitra and Slovakia generally is not professionalised and most NGOs work on a voluntary basis

6.5. Emerging recommendations: city-specific, comparative among the cities, general

In the conclusion of the Inclusive Transformation Plan for Nitra pilot we list the following recommendations answering to challenges encountered that are based on experiences, feedback from stakeholders and results we were able to obtain by carrying out described tasks under WP4 and relevant transversal WPs:

- To maintain interest of local stakeholders for what is a relatively long process of co-design, the progress of the process should be communicated frequently. Early co-deployment and testing of certain solutions was used to give the stakeholders and local community the "taste of the VIS" and keep them interested and involved (e.g. workshops with Botanical Garden and Cuketa NGO at Hidepark for Roma schoolchildren).
- To ensure more effective co-deployment process that requires continuous communication an IN-HUB Office will be established at the SUA partner premises where both LCAs (from HIDE and SUA), local WP4 coordinator and co-design facilitator will be available all day during Thursdays and Fridays. This will improve communication between project partners, but also towards IN-HUB members.
- To establish synergic effects with other initiatives and development of policies on the city level IN-HABIT Nitra team members are and will continue to be involved in other working groups (e.g. working group that prepared new Cultural and Creative Industries Strategy for 2021-2031, working group preparing a bid for Nitra during their candidacy for ECoC, working group preparing new Urban plan with Office of Chief Architect, working group preparing a plan for complex revitalisation of old section of the City Park, working group preparing ITI proposals for next programming period to be funded from EU structural funds etc.)
- Some methodological issues of measuring impacts of proposed solutions may arise. Impacts assessment related issues in case of Nitra pilot arise mostly due to potential difficulties of differentiating and demarcating intervention and control group. This is caused by two reasons. First the scope and nature of intervention area is such that is not only used by inhabitants of one clearly demarcated neighbourhood, but also by inhabitants of other city districts, even tourist and visitors. Other issue is, that at this stage communities from other neighbourhoods of the city as well as organisations and institutions expressed interest in taking part mostly in planned soft activities and their "refusal" would go against the inclusion principles and values of the project. This issue will be mitigated by setting up a system of recording contacts (personal information and emails) of everyone participating in IN-HABIT related activities, thus building a database of intervention group members to be later contacted during the interim and ex-post evaluation of the impacts regardless of their residency.
- There is a risk of potentially building "cathedrals in the desert" – Since planned VIS are to be concentrated in certain localities in the pilot area targeting certain vulnerable and disadvantaged groups, there is a risk that although the project will bring benefits to these specific localities

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and specific vulnerable groups, it will not have a synergic and integrative effect on the whole community. This can pose a risk of decreased sustainability of the solutions and in some cases even increase of the isolation of certain target groups. This is why during the future co-design process and co-deployment partners and involved stakeholders should focus greatly on mobility and open-source nature of its individual VIS. This means that although deployed in certain localities where target groups congregate, they can be moved and used in other parts of the pilot area and even outside of the pilot area. This feature of the REMOULD concept will be demonstrated during the co-deployment of the soft solutions.

- In order to battle Covid-19 related restrictive measures, partners will continue to develop online co-design tools (like the 3D mapping software Kuula) to reach stakeholders during times when it's impossible to meet, and will develop monetary and non-monetary incentives for local observers and IN-HUB members that initiated more intensive involvement in the WP4 tasks (e.g. organising their own "spin-off" co-design activities with groups project partners and IN-HUB are not able to reach).
- ITP should be an open and flexible document, periodically re-evaluated and up-dated along with specific VIS in accordance to the changing local situation (e.g. since large portion of economic migrants in Nitra are from Ukraine and after the recent Russian invasion of the country, the city of Nitra is expecting an influx of refugees, who will seek shelter near their friends and families living here. This will invariably change the current situation of one of our major target groups and should be reflected in adaptation of relevant VIS that could be employed to alleviate new emerging issues in the city and pilot area).

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Appendixes

Appendix 1 Nitra City profile

Figure 1.1 Origin of Nitra City population in 2021

Source: own elaboration based on Statistical Office of SR data

Figure 1.2 Origin of Nitra City registered migrant population in 2019

EU/ECC countries

Non-EU/ECC countries

Figure 1.3 Nitra City migrant population according to declared reasons for stay, type of residence, gender and age

Source: own elaboration based on Statistical Office of SR data

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Figure 1.4 Migration balance in Nitra Region, Nitra District and City of Nitra

Source: own elaboration based on Statistical Office of SR data

Figure 1.5 Origin and current residence of Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra graduates (year of graduation 2013 – 2017)

Source: own elaboration based on prior research

Figure 1.6 Migration trajectories of Nitra’s students and graduates

Source: own elaboration based on prior research

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Appendix 2 Dražovce district profile

Table 2.1 Population structure of Dražovce district and comparison with Nitra City

Indicator	Dražovce	Nitra City
Total number of inhabitants	1 874	77 358
Women	50.48 %	52.51 %
Men	49.47 %	47.47 %
Pre-productive age	14.30 %	14.29 %
Productive age	63.88 %	62.02 %
Post-productive age	21.77 %	24.54 %

Source: own elaboration based on Nitra City Hall internal data

Figure 2.1 Challenges in Dražovce district

District Dražovce in 2015

District Dražovce in 2018

Source: Archinfo, 2019

Roma community housing in Dražovce, 2021

Segregated Roma elementary school in Dražovce, 2021

Source: own analysis

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Appendix 3 Stakeholder mapping process

Figure 3.1 Preliminary stakeholder map and their potential contribution

Source: own elaboration

Figure 3.2 Stakeholder map in November 2020

Source: own elaboration

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Figure 3.3 Stakeholder map in March 2021 (LCA training)

Source: own elaboration

Figure 3.4 Stakeholder map in November 2021 (Launch of the IN-HUBs)

Source: own elaboration

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Figure 3.5 Current stakeholder map in February 2022 (Final IN-HUB structure)

Source: own elaboration

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Appendix 4 IN-HUB organisational structure

What	Key roles	Partners	Stakeholders	Decision-making
Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local coordinator for WP4: SUA - LCA SUA - LCA HIDE - User Advisory board: institutional and individual representatives of target groups - Other: Institutional Support and Oversight, Affiliated Stakeholders - 6 Advisory Groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Partners: SUA, NITRA, HIDE - International (transversal) partners: TSR, UREAD, ISIM, BOT - Local administration & departments: Project and Strategic Management Department 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Stakeholder map - Key stakeholders - Missing or underrepresented actors (Roma community) - How to include issues of underrepresented groups (through local Roma segregated school and teachers) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - on project partner level based on consensus between representatives of SUA, NITRA, HIDE - on UAB and IN-HUB level: based on bilateral negotiations and consensus
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication manager: SUA - Social media manager: SUA, HIDE - Key local contacts (KLC): SUA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Partners: SUA, HIDE, NITRA - International (transversal) partners: BOT - Local administration & departments: Project and Strategic Management Department, Department of Communication and Promotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selected audiences and target groups: general public and target groups as defined - Channels & media contacts (social media of local partners, TV NITRIČKA, other) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KLC employed by SUA serves as communication manager and together with LCA HIDE as IN-HABIT related social media manager - social media manager of PP NITRA provides support
Co-design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LCA HIDE - Designers & technicians: SUA FHLE, Botanical Garden, AgroBioTech - Facilitators: SUA FHLE, FESRD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Partners: SUA, HIDE, NITRA - International (transversal) partners: TSR, DFC, LABORELEC - Local administration & departments: Dpt of Education, Dpt of Environment, Dpt of Social Services, Dtp of Transport, Dpt of Culture, Office of Chief Architect 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Targeted beneficiaries: vulnerable groups and special users - Knowledge and service providers - Community leaders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - selection and prioritizing VIS on Core IN-HUB level based on consensus - specific VIS based on bilateral negotiations with members of 3 sections of IN-HUB
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LCA HIDE, LCA SUA - Local observers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PP involved in the implementation of VIS on field: SUA, HIDE, NITRA, TSR, UREAD, BOT, WTG - Local administration and departments: as previous - Private contractors and providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providers - Contractors - Volunteers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - specific VIS based on bilateral negotiations and contracts with members of 3 sections of IN-HUB, and relevant procurement procedures
Impact Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP7 Leader: ISIM - LCA SUA - Local observers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Partners: SUA, NITRA 		
Gender landscape / GDEI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP6 Leader: UREAD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Partners: SUA, NITRA 		

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Appendix 5 Profiles of institutional members of UAB in Core IN-HUB Nitra

Stakeholder	Profile
Civic Association CUKETA	Engaged in educational activities, natural gardening, permaculture, culinary activities, organization of various community-educational events, manufacture of natural cosmetics and cleaning products, production and design of sustainable and educational elements e.g. design and creation of edible school and community spaces ("Spaces for Creatures"), and multifunctional elements that are healing, aesthetic, educational, natural, recycled. They also run the community garden at cultural and community centre Hidepark.
Civic Association "Let's Cycle Nitra!"	Supports modern yet ecological way of life in the city of Nitra, building awareness of cycling as a transport of the future, improving the conditions and position of cyclists in the city, helping, consulting and recommending the best solutions for building the cycling infrastructure in Nitra. They also offer educational and motivational seminars on safe bicycle transport around the city as well as provide solutions to scepticism with use of alternative mobility patterns.
Civic Association Mareena	Focuses on connecting locals and foreigners through volunteering programmes, courses, workshops and other community activities, and closely cooperates with local charities. They provide opportunities for active integration of foreigners into Slovak society, support the local community of Slovaks and foreigners in establishing relationships, raise public awareness of the issues of diversity, migration and integration. They regularly conduct Slovak conversation courses for foreigners, English and computer skills courses as well as socio-cultural orientation workshops.
Civic Association STORM	Works in an area of prevention of risky behaviour and socio-pathological phenomena of different target groups on the local level based on low-threshold principles and in the terms of philosophy of Harm Reduction. They are the only accredited subject of Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic in this field and they work in three towns, grouping people interested in preventive work, preparing and distributing materials aimed at prevention of risky behaviour like various forms of addiction. They cooperate closely with health facilities, interest, youth, civic and other associations, charities, public administration and local police.
Independent Atelier 37	Creative atelier bringing together professional and amateur artists and creatives in areas of photography, filmmaking marketing, cultural production, graphics etc.
Pomáhajko, o.z.	Family run non-profit collecting clothes, food, or a drugstore from people and distributing it to children, pensioners, people in need. Supports children's homes, social services facilities and families with children with disabilities. As part of their activities, we also take care of Dražovce, collect waste in public spaces and wooded areas, organizing creative workshops for children and pensioners, where they integrate children and people with disabilities.
Creative centre Nitra	Newly established Creative Center Nitra aims to support the development of the creative talent and skills and provide tools for the business development in the field of cultural and creative industries. Priority areas are performing arts, crafts, visual arts, music, multimedia, audiovisual creation, providing a complex development of the capacities (capacity building).
OZ Pestrec	Produces zero waste products and provides environmental education for schools, special events and other activities with themes ranging from waste, transport to shopping, food and the ecological footprint.
Botanical Garden Nitra (affiliated with SUA)	The garden serves as an educational and research facility, specialized in: garden and landscape-architectural dendrology; interior and exterior floristry; fruit growing, including the presentation of old, Slovak regional varieties and lesser-known fruit species; viticulture; vegetable growing; medicinal and tonic plants; rescue of endangered and disappearing species of indigenous flora in Slovakia.
AgroBioTech (affiliated with SUA)	The AgroBioTech Research Centre (ABT RC) is a specialized facility which performs concentrated innovative research in the relevant fields aimed at conducting new methods and procedures in research, especially within applied research, with the express goal of transferring its results into practice. It covers fields of agrobiolgy, the processing technology of agricultural products and the agri-food industry, biotechnology, genetic technologies, agroecology, bioenergetics, and bioeconomy.
Elementary school Dražovce	Elementary school with 107 pupils and 17 teachers (the only one located in District Dražovce). Mostly Roma children attend the school.
Elementary school Tulipánová	Elementary school with 445 pupils and 63 employees situated close to the City Park and the river Nitra.
HidePumpa NGO	The association operates a community cycling workshop and a pump-track. In the cycle workshop, they organize educational workshops focused on bicycle repair and offer material and tools for bicycle repair to the general public.
Ice bears NGO	The civic association unites the community of winter swimmers in the city of Nitra. They organize several meetings a year at various bodies of water (Lake in the Park, Zobor Lake), improving their health and resistance to disease. The association also has an educational dimension.
District NGO	The association is dedicated to art in public space, preparation of educational activities, raising awareness of the need and possibilities of object art in the city of Nitra.

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Appendix 6 Profile of institutional members of Affiliated Stakeholders group

Stakeholder	Profile
COMIN	Co-founded by the City of Nitra and Nitra Community Foundation. Provides services within the Point of First Contact for foreigners and citizens of Nitra, social and legal counselling for foreigners and help in crisis situations, low-threshold language education for foreigners connected with intercultural orientation, as well as leisure and volunteer programs for social inclusion.
Nitra Community Foundation	Implements Nitra City's participatory budget via a grant program financing innovative public benefit activities and creative ideas of citizens of Nitra called "I'm changing my city". They also co-founded the COMIN. We are sharing information and databases and coordinating complimentary activities.
Architects Association Nitra	Encompasses architects from all sorts of fields from urban to landscape. They organise within Architecture Day each year walks, excursions, bike trips, lectures with engaging explanations by experts, or workshops on topics of industrial heritage, housing estates, historic buildings, as well as public space, urban greenery, use of the waterfront or the availability of housing. They organize Hackaton which connected Nitra with architects, landscape engineers, but also with students, to discuss ideas on debarrierization of the park, mobile green wall, demarcation of lines of historic buildings, rest pavilion with gallery and cafe, shading modules.
Nitra Volunteer Centre	A non-profit organization whose main mission is to spread awareness of volunteering. Recruiting volunteers, informing about the possibilities and benefits of volunteering. Offers training, consultation and assistance in choosing the right form of volunteering for each individual and training companies that have decided to work with volunteers and networking organizations and volunteers. In the future they will help the IN-HUB with contacting and organising activities with volunteer participation.
International Theatre festival "Divadelná Nitra"	The largest yearly theatre festival in the region (even outside Slovakia). They have extended experiences with participatory approaches in performing arts, are a part of the Be SpectACTive! a large-scale European cooperation project which operates in performing arts through artistic productions and participatory practices aimed at involving the citizens and spectators in creative and organisational processes. During the festival they organise accompanying event in public spaces across the city (which would be a good channel for replication and dissemination of tested interventions), we consult them with co-design activities, and use their spaces for workshops.
Sekáč	Second-hand at the pedestrian zone in the city centre, which sells second-hand clothes. These are textiles that are carefully selected, with an emphasis on quality material and design, especially from the UK. In addition, the owner recycles old men's shirts and a bag for designer pieces for women. They also organize various educational events on slow fashion, sustainable fashion, as well as SWAPs, where they offer space for the sale of textiles to their customers.
NGO I care	The civic association is engaged in the recycling and upcycling of 4 types of waste, education about waste and its impact on the environment, the production of design textile elements using the linorite technique, the production of various objects from molten plastics, etc.
Episcopacy Nitra	The Diocese of Nitra is a Christian organization which, among other things, manages the property of the Roman Catholic Church in Nitra, establishes churches and services for the practitioners.
Arriva Nitra	The transport company is engaged in the operation of bike sharing for the general public in the summer months, while bicycles have stands in several places in the city centre and bicycles can be rented for min. 1 hour for a fee.
Adoreal s.r.o.	The company sells canoes and boats of the Osagian Canoe brand, which are used for rafting on the river. It is specific thanks to the unique construction, material used and processing, which are the result of a 50-year tradition of production.
Drum show NGO	The association is dedicated to organizing drumming workshops for children and adults, in various drum styles, such as Brazilian drums, African drums, etc. They also cooperate with the Hidepark association with the city of Nitra on workshops for children (also) from disadvantaged groups, as well as on the Urbact OnStage project.
The Department of Ethnology and Folklore Studies (UCF)	Provides education in the field of ethnology, development of the traditional culture, socio-normative culture, socio-cultural background of the Slovak regions development, the culture of ethnic minorities and cultural heritage of regions. Educator involved from the Department organizes various workshops for voice and sound movement techniques (body melody), which are based on traditional Slovak songs in an innovative way.
Initiative Night run Nitra	This informal initiative brings together the people of Nitra who are dedicated to running. Every Wednesday evening they go to a joint run in different parts of the city.
KINOKLUB	KinoKlub Nitra focuses mainly on art and club films, but also on popular classics and various film festivals. Over the years it has gained many fans, who are shown films on a regular basis, currently in the Nitra synagogue and during summer also at Hidepark.
NGO IRV/ROK	The non-profit organization IRV/ROK, which stands for Initiative for Regional Education, focuses on environmental topics with an emphasis on sustainability, combining ecological, social and economic dimensions. It seeks to open up ideas that support the transformation of the current system into a sustainable one in order to strengthen community mind-sets.

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Elementary Art School ATELIER MEDEA	Art school in the centre of Nitra, which was first established as a project in 2000 and later accredited by the Ministry of Education. This leisure facility is dedicated to children, youth, but also adults, where they work with various techniques such as drawing, painting, graphics or clay modelling and their combination.
Secondary School of Art Design	The private art school offers a varied selection of fields of study such as interior design, virtual graphics, conservation and restoration, as well as graphic and photographic design.
Jaguar Land Rover	In 2018, a Jaguar Land Rover Slovakia plant became part of the extensive industrial park in Nitra. The company currently employs over 3,800 staff and is continually creating new job opportunities in a variety of roles across all production areas. It employs large number of economic migrants from Ukraine and Balkan countries. One of the biggest employers in the industrial park that is part of the pilot area.
MH Invest, llc	MH Invest is a company established the Ministry of Economy of the Slovak Republic, carrying out activities related to the preparation and construction of industrial parks and zones for investors, in cooperation with state institutions, local authorities, network administrators and investors. It ensures the preparation of the territory and purchase of land for investors and related works with the construction of infrastructure for regional development. Important due to ownership relations within the pilot area.
Západoslovenská vodárenská spoločnosť, a.s.	The main activity of West Slovak Water Company based in Nitra is to supply the population, industry, agriculture and other consumers with drinking water from public water supply systems in the given territorial jurisdiction, to divert and treat waste water discharged into public sewers in the given territorial jurisdiction, to operate, maintain, repair and protect water sources, public water supply systems, public sewers and sewage treatment plants, to provide water management and technical development, hydrogeological surveys, testing, measurement, analysis and control, etc.
Creative Centre SPU (affiliated with SUA)	The main objective of the CC SPU is to mobilise and support the creative potential in the Nitra region, to build a favourable environment for the development of creative talent and non-technological innovations, which can help to stimulate employment and job creation in the cultural and creative industries. The Centre is prioritised on three sectors of the creative industries - design, architecture, sustainable advertising and marketing.

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Appendix 7 Time frame of COVID-19 pandemic development and restrictions in Nitra

Explanations:

- (*) under hard lockdown we understand restriction of movement for more than 6 hours per day, restriction of movement between borders of districts in country, interruption of services other than basic services, period of hardly recommended home-office to all, and prohibition of group meeting other than consisting of family members only
- (**) under soft lockdown we understand restriction of movement for less than 6 hours per day, partial restriction on the provision of services, collection and organization of events not exceeding a maximum number of participants (differs in from 10-100 participants)

Detail:

- Hard restriction of movement = 16.03.20. - 21.04.20. / 19.12.20. - 19.04.21.
- Soft restriction of movement = 16.03.20 - 06.05.20. / 24.10.20 - 26.04.21. / 5.11.21. - 12.01.22. / 19.01.22. - present
- Distant education on universities = 16.03.20. - 31.08.21. / 01.11.21. - present
- Forced home-office = 16.03.20 - 06.05.20 / 30.11.21. - 31.05.21. / 29.11.21. - 24.01.22.
- Positivity in team = 09.12.2020, 01.02.2022

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Appendix 8 City-specific IHW indicators

Social well-being

Sub-dimension	Exp. change (P= partners' view / I= inhabitants' view)	Indicator	Description
Social cohesion	Improved social relations (P; I)	Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood	Persons who declare a good/very good level of satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood/living area (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Increased trust among people (P)	Trust in others	persons who declare a good/very good level of trust in other persons within their community (Qualitative/Self Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Reduced social conflict (P)	Social conflicts	Persons who have experienced or witnessed conflicts among persons or groups in their neighbourhood (Qualitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
Perception of security	Increased sense of safety (P; I)	sense of safety at night	Persons who feel safe walking at night in the city (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		fear of road accidents	Persons who express fear to be victim of road accidents when walking or cycling in the street of their neighbourhood (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		sense of safety in green areas	Persons who feel safe to walk in the public green areas of their neighbourhood (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area	Average level of crime, violence and vandalism in the neighbourhood perceived by persons on a range from 1-10 (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
Social Inclusion	Increased social relations in public spaces (P; I)	Contact with others in public spaces	Persons who get together with friends and relatives in public spaces once a week (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Domestic Isolation	Persons who spend the majority of their time alone at home (Qualitative/self reported/Key impact indicator)
	Improved sense of inclusion (P; I)	Sense of inclusion	Persons who feel to be part of the community (Quantitative and qualitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Improved civil engagement and democratic participation (P)	Civil engagement 1
	Civil engagement 2		persons who believe they can influence local policies/political decisions (Qualitative/Self Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved social engagement (P; I)	Social engagement 1	persons who declare to participate in voluntary activities (social, cultural, educational, religious) (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Social engagement 2	persons who are satisfied with their level of involvement in the local community life (Qualitative/Self Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Social engagement 3	People who are committed to take care of public spaces and green areas in their neighbourhood (Qualitative/Self Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
Increased change-making attitude (P)	Change-making attitude	Persons who believe they can change the reality of their neighbourhood (social situation, beauty/attractiveness of the space, economic situation)	
Equality	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Sense of being treated equally	Persons who feel they are treated with less courtesy and respect than others (or other groups) (Qualitative/Self reported/Context indicator)
		Access to internet from home	Persons who have access to internet from home (Quantitative/Self reported/Context Indicator)

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	Improved equal access to culture and leisure (P; I)	Equal access to culture and leisure	Persons who believe to have the same opportunity than others to access the available cultural and leisure opportunities in their city/neighbourhood (Qualitative/Self Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Obstacles for the access to culture and leisure	Persons who think to have economic, time, family, mobility, cognitive, cultural obstacles in the access to culture and leisure opportunities in their City/neighbourhood (Quantitative and qualitative/Self reported /context Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Obstacles for the access to training opportunities	Persons who think to have economic, time, family, mobility, cognitive, linguistic/cultural, social obstacles in the access to training opportunities in their city (qualitative and quantitative/Self reported /context Indicator)
Discrimination	Decreased perception of discrimination in society (P)	Perception of discrimination in society	Persons who believe that minority groups are considered dangerous/dishonest/ criminals/ unreliable/ bad neighbours by local inhabitants (qualitative/Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Perceived personal condition of discrimination	Persons who can describe themselves as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in their country. (qualitative/Self reported /context Indicator)
Spatial well-being	Improved accessibility of local resources (P; I)	Accessibility of local resources	Persons who think in their neighbourhood is easy to find help from others; find job opportunities; training opportunities; find safe, pleasant and accessible green areas, participate in cultural events; find adequate social and health assistance, find a place to do sports, find healthy food, find children playgrounds, moving on foot, moving by bike (Qualitative and Quantitative /Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved satisfaction with urban green areas (P; I)	Satisfaction with urban green areas	persons who are satisfied with public green areas of their neighbourhood in terms of accessibility, safety, inclusiveness, beauty, comfort (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased inclusiveness of public squares and green areas (P; I)	Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas	Persons who feel free to access, to use and to move within the public squares and green areas in their neighbourhood (Quantitative and qualitative/Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved air quality perception (P)	Air pollution perception	Persons who think that the quality of air in their neighbourhood is satisfactory/good (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Decreased noise pollution perception (P)	Perception of noise pollution	Persons who think that in their neighbourhood is easy to find places/areas where the noise is not high (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Improved sense of belonging and satisfaction with the quality of the neighbourhood (P; I)	Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood	Number of persons who like their neighbourhood; who think that it has a good reputation; who think that the image of the neighbourhood has improved in the past two years; who think it could attract more tourists in the next years; who would not move to another neighbourhood (Qualitative and Quantitative /Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)

Healthy lifestyles

Sub-dimension	Exp. change (P= partners' view / I= inhabitants' view)	Indicator	Description
Physical health status	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Self-reported health status	Average level of physical health reported by persons on a 5 points scales (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
Determinants of health	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Practice of physical activity	Frequency of practice of physical activity in a week (Quantitative /Self reported / context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time spent on food preparation at home	Average time spent by persons preparing their meals at home in a day (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	Increased consumption of self-grown fruit and vegetables (P)	Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption	Persons who declare to consume self-grown fruit and vegetables (Qualitative/Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)

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	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Consumption of fruits and vegetables	Persons who declare to consume fresh fruits and vegetables on a daily basis (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Access to healthy and nutritious food	Persons who were unable to eat healthy and nutritious food in the last week (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
Sports practice	Increased satisfaction with sports facilities (I)	Satisfaction with sports facilities	Persons who are satisfied with the areas and facilities devoted to sports in their neighbourhood (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased practice of sports in public green areas (P; I)	Practice of sports in public green areas	Frequency of use of the public outdoor/green areas to do sports in a week (Quantitative and qualitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased perception of benefits from sports (I)	Benefits from sports	Persons who think that sports/physical activity contributes to their well-being (qualitative/Self reported /Key impact indicator)
Cultural consumption and production	Increased satisfaction with cultural facilities (P; I)	Satisfaction with cultural facilities	Persons who are satisfied with the cultural places/events and opportunities in their neighbourhood (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased participation in cultural activities within public spaces (P)	Participation in cultural activities within public spaces (outdoor/indoor)	Frequency of participation in cultural activities/consumptions in public squares, green areas, centres of their neighbourhood in a week (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased perception of benefits from culture (P)	Benefits from culture	Persons who think that cultural activity contributes to their well-being (qualitative/Self reported /Key impact indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Cultural consumptions	Average time devoted to cultural consumptions during the week (theatre, reading books, cinema, exhibitions) (Quantitative/self reported/context indicator)
	Increased local cultural engagement (P)	Local cultural engagement	Persons directly involved in the organization, production and management of cultural activities, products, places and events in their neighbourhood (Quantitative self reported/ key impact indicator)
Leisure/Free time	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to leisure and personal care	Average time (hours) devoted to leisure and personal care in a typical working day (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	Increased practice of healthy leisure (I)	Practice of healthy leisure	People who practice healthy behaviours for leisure /avoid unhealthy leisure (Qualitative /Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	Increased time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas (P; I)	Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas	Average time (hours) spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas in a day (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased benefits from urban nature	Benefits from urban nature	Persons who think that urban nature contributes to their well-being (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
	Increased time spent in social and recreational public spaces (P; I)	Time spent in social and recreational public spaces	Average time spent in social and recreational public spaces in a day (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to family care	Average time in a day devoted to family care (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to pets' care/playing with pets	Average time devoted to pets' care/playing with pets in a day (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Satisfaction with free time use	Persons who are satisfied with the quality of their free time/the way they spend their free time (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	Improved perception of the quality of one's free time in public spaces (I)	Perceived quality of free time in public spaces	Persons who think that the quality of their free time in public spaces is satisfactory (Qualitative self reported/key impact indicator)
	Increased perception of benefits from social and recreational public space (P)	Benefits from social and recreational public spaces	Persons who think that social and recreational public spaces contribute to their well-being (Qualitative self reported/key impact indicator)

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Economic well-being

Sub-dimension	Exp. change (P= partners' view / I= inhabitants' view)	Indicator	Description
Employment	Increased employment of people (P, I)	Opportunity to find a job in the city	Persons who are satisfied with the opportunities offered by the job market at city level (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
		Expected sector of occupation	Persons who think they can find a job in NBS related sector in the next 6 months (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
	Increased satisfaction with one's skills and competences (P)	Satisfaction with one's own competencies, skills 1	persons who are satisfied with their level of skills and competences (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
		Satisfaction with one's own competencies, skills 2	Persons who think that their education, skills and competences will be helpful to find a paid job in the city (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
Financial situation	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Feeling that one's basic needs are met	Persons who believe that their basics needs are sufficiently met (Quantitative/Self reported /context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Satisfaction with time and resources for personal care	Number of persons who think to have sufficient resources to manage personal matters/personal care (Quantitative/Self reported /context indicator)
	Increased satisfaction with one's surroundings and living environment (P; C)	Satisfaction with one's surroundings/living environment	Satisfaction related to one's own surroundings/living environment (qualitative/Self reported /Key impact indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Satisfactions with one's own financial situation	Average level of satisfaction related to one's own family or individual income and resources (Quantitative/Self reported /context indicator)

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Appendix 9 Secondary IHW data

DIMENSION	SUB-DIMENSION	CONTEXT INDICATOR	Availability	REFER E-NCE YEAR	SOURCE	Level (neighbourhood, city, district, region)	
DEMOGRAPHY		Resident Population	real time data	2021	municipal data, klient.nitra.sk	neighbourhood	
		Deaths		2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city	
		Life Expectancy		2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	district	
		Immigration (rate or number of individuals)		2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city	
		Emigration rate (rate or number of individuals)		2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city	
		Household composition 1 – number of families with more than 5 persons	population census (data available in 10-year intervals)	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city	
		Household composition 2 – average number of persons per family	population census (data available in 10-year intervals)	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city	
		Household composition 3 – number of persons living alone	population census (data available in 10-year intervals)	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city	
SOCIAL WELL-BEING	ATTITUDES TOWARDS EQUALITY	Attitudes towards equality (any indicator)	not available				
	ATTITUDES TOWARDS PUBLIC SPACE	Attitudes towards public spaces (any indicator)	not available				
	PARTICIPATION AND CIVIC ENGAGEMENT	Participation in local initiatives/NGOs, social/charitable, environmental, and political	not available				
	USE OF COMMUNAL SPACES	frequency of use of communal areas (public garden, community centre)	not available				
	EDI POLICIES	Existence of EDI policies/plans in local government			2021	Nitra Municipal Office	city
		Number of NGOs active for the protection of rights of LGBTIQ+ people	only their name and NACE code is available, not their field of action in this degree of specificity		2021	Register of organisations of Slovak Republic	city
		NUMBER OF NGOS ACTIVE ON DIVERSITY, EQUITY AND INCLUSION	only their name and NACE code is available, not their field of action in this degree of specificity		2021	Register of organisations of Slovak Republic	city
		individuals in local assemblies	number of city council members depend on population size, so we chose ratio of citizens to council members in city districts committees		2021	municipal data	city
		individuals in local government posts			2021	municipal data	city
		Intentional homicide rate			2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city

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	CRIME, DISCRIMINATION AND VIOLENCE	Number of discrimination cases	no data on discrimination cases, depending on where discrimination took place (e.g. workplace, access to facilities) different institutions handle this, and usually it is handled in-house			
		Hate crime rate	data may not be relevant, as the "hate" component in crime is very hard to prove, so it may be hidden, police district Nitra covers neighbouring small district	6. 2017 - 6. 2018	Ministry of Interior of Slovak Republic	district
		Percentage of women victim of domestic violence	no data on domestic violence, crime data is registered according to the paragraphs of the Criminal Code, so this is "hidden" under other criminal activity, police district Nitra covers neighbouring small district	6. 2017 - 6. 2018	Ministry of Interior of Slovak Republic	district
ECONOMIC WELL-BEING	POVERTY AND INCOME	Poverty rate		2020	EU SILC	region
	ACCESS TO SERVICES	Individuals assisted by social care services		2020	Institute of Social Policy (Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family)	region
		Access to broad band internet connection		2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
		Individuals in need of care	not available	2020	Institute of Social Policy (Ministry of LSAF)	region
		Individuals who have used formal care services in last 12 months		2020	Institute of Social Policy (Ministry LSAF)	region
	INCOME	Average income (it could be hourly, monthly, annual)	Average nominal monthly earnings of employees in EUR	2019	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	district
	HOUSING	Home ownership rate				
		% and number of homes/apartments in private ownership	based on housing census	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
		% and number of households in which at least one member of the household is the owner of a dwelling unit	based on population census	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
		Private rental rate				
		% and number of homes/apartments rented	based on housing census	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
		% and number of households in which at least one member of the household is the renter of a dwelling unit	based on population census	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
		Social Housing rate		2021	Municipal office	city
	EDUCATION	Percentage of individuals having primary education	population census (data available in 10-year intervals)	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
		Percentage of individuals having secondary education	population census (data available in 10-year intervals)	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
		Percentage of individuals having tertiary education (university and post-graduate degree)	population census (data available in 10-year intervals)	2011	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
	EMPLOYMENT	Employment rate		2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	district
Part-Time/Full-time employment		only full time employment	2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city	
Employees by flexibility of their working schedule		not available				
Self-employment			2020	Register of organisations of Slovak Republic	city	

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		Unemployment rate		2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	district
		Registered job seekers (measure of registered unemployment)		2021	Central Office of Labor, Social Affairs and Family	city
		Activity/Participation rate		2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	city
		Neet rate (percentage of young people between 15 and 24 years who are not in employment, education or training)	registered job seekers	2021	Central Office of Labor, Social Affairs and Family	city
		Time devoted to unpaid care work	not available			
		Black and grey job rate	not available			
		CONSUMPTION	CULTURAL/LEISURE CONSUMPTIONS	data only available as average monthly consumption in EUR for culture and recreation (includes sports)	2019	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic
	SPORTS CONSUMPTION	not available				
HEALTHY LIFESTYLES	TIME USE	Average time spent with family and relatives (in person)	not available			
		Average time spent with family and relatives (via social media)	not available			
	HEALTH DETERMINANTS	Individuals doing sporting/cultural/leisure activities	not available			
		Fruit and vegetable consumption	available only on national level			
		Consumption of tobacco rate (persons over 15)	available only on national level			
		Percentage of persons with obesity and overweight	not available			
		Individual average alcohol consumption (litre/year)	available only on national level			
		Number of persons with eating disorders assisted by local health services	not available			
		Number of persons with mental disorders assisted by local health services	not available			
	MOBILITY	Average time spent travelling from home to work and back	not available			
		Mode of transport/commuting to work: car		2018	Sustainable Mobility Plan of Nitra City	city
		Mode of transport/commuting to work: public transport		2018	Sustainable Mobility Plan of Nitra City	city
		Mode of transport/commuting to work: walk		2018	Sustainable Mobility Plan of Nitra City	city
		Mode of transport/commuting to work: bicycle		2018	Sustainable Mobility Plan of Nitra City	city
		Mode of transport/commuting to work: motorbike	not available			
		Mode of transport/commuting to work: other		2018	Sustainable Mobility Plan of Nitra City	city
		People killed in road accidents		2020	Ministry of Interior of Slovak Republic	city
MENTAL HEALTH	Suicide rate – mortality by suicide over 100.000 inhab.	(police district Nitra covers neighbouring small district)	2020	Statistical Office of Slovak Republic	district	
	I cannot work because of poor health	not available				
	Weekly minutes moderate activities	not available				
	Future looks good	not available				
	How often feels isolated from others	not available				
	Feels calm and peaceful	not available				
	Has a lot of energy	not available				
	Feels downhearted and depressed	not available				
	Satisfaction with life overall	not available				
	Feels optimistic about the future	not available				

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Appendix 10 Key findings from the baseline survey – Nitra

Social well-being

People living or frequenting one of the neighbourhoods listed in Q2 of the survey Intervention Group	The rest of the inhabitants of Nitra Control Group
Equality and discrimination	
Perceive a sense of inequality and discrimination based on ethnicity and age	
21% perceive themselves to be a member of a discriminated group	Vs 10% of respondents in the control group
51% report having no difficulty accessing cultural and leisure opportunities in the city	Vs 68% of respondents in the control group
93% declare to have access to internet from home	Vs 99% of respondents in the control group
Social Cohesion	
Experience satisfaction with personal relationships and trust in others, by reporting kindness and solidarity from neighbours	
75% are satisfied of their relationship with people living in their neighbourhood	Vs 69% of respondents in the control group
43% consider easy finding help from others in their neighbourhood	Vs 57% of respondents in the control group
Perceive social conflicts between Slovaks and immigrants as well as with the Roma community	
39% trust in the capacity of local authorities to maintain peace and security in the neighbourhood	Vs 60% of respondents in the control group
Cultural participation and engagement	
widespread presence of cultural organizations and association, cultural events and movements, However, this cultural vitality is mainly concentrated in the old city centre and in Hidepark	
51% report having no difficulty accessing cultural and leisure opportunities in their neighbourhood	Vs 68% of respondents in the control group
24% attend cultural activities organized in public and green spaces of their neighbourhood once a week or more	Vs 22% of respondents in the control group
30% report engaging in neighbourhood cultural or voluntary activities once a month or more	Vs 16% of respondents in the control group
elderly, persons with disabilities and people living outside the city centre (or far from Hidepark) experience mobility obstacles in the access to culture	
Young people and ethnic minorities lack adequate cultural offer for them in terms of quality as well as in terms of inclusive cultural spaces	
Perception of security	
Experience a low sense of safety at night, fear of road accidents and thefts	
36% consider walking alone after dark to be safe	Vs 57% of respondents in the control group
66% consider walking alone during the day to be safe	Vs 89% of respondents in the control group
64% consider walking in public green areas to be safe	Vs 80% of respondents in the control group
56% agree that it often happens to them observing vandalism damages to urban furnishings and private properties	Vs 51% of respondents in the control group
41% consider leaving a vehicle unattended to be unsafe	vs 51% of respondents in the control group
69% are concerned by the risk of road accidents while walking or cycling on the street.	vs 47% of respondents in the control group
Social inclusion	
Experience frequent contact with others in public spaces and good sense of community and satisfaction with their level of involvement in the local community	
66% report meeting frequently with friends and relatives in public spaces (once a month or more)	Vs 65% of respondents in the control group

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60% think that feeling a sense of community with people in one's neighbourhood is important or very important	Vs 55% of respondents in the control group
29% agree that in their neighbourhood no one is left alone	Vs 40% of respondents in the control group
However, the group of immigrant workers suffers a stable condition of severe domestic isolation and social exclusion	
Experience low levels of civic engagement, a low sense of trust in institutions as well as in the possibility to influence local political decisions	
14% report engaging in democratic life at city level through committees and councils once a month or more	Vs 7% of respondents in the control group
experience a moderate level of social engagement and change making attitude since they believe it is easier to change the life in the neighbourhood from the bottom	
52% engage in community problem solving when a problem arises	Vs 38% of respondents in the control group
30% report engaging in neighbourhood cultural or voluntary activity at least once a month	Vs 16% of respondents in the control group
20% take care of public green areas as volunteers at least once a month	Vs 14% of respondents in the control group
Spatial well-being	
Accessibility of local resources	
Participants from the control group report a better accessibility of local resources in the neighbourhood	
49% consider easy participating in cultural events	vs 64% of respondents in the control group
39% consider easy to find adequate social and health assistance	vs 64% of respondents in the control group
57% consider easy to find a green area to do sports	vs 76% of respondents in the control group
57% consider easy to find safe, accessible, and pleasant green areas	vs 74% of respondents in the control group
50% consider easy to find healthy food	Vs 66% of respondents in the control group
75% consider easy moving on foot	Vs 91% of respondents in the control group
70% consider easy moving by bike	Vs 81% of respondents in the control group
Satisfaction with urban green areas	
62% agree that the public green areas when they spent the majority of their time are frequented by people of all ages	Vs 81% of respondents in the control group
61% agree that such public green areas are frequented by people of all ethnicities	vs 64% of respondents in the control group
34% agree that such public green areas are accessible for persons with disabilities	vs 64% of respondents in the control group
54% agree that such public green areas are a pleasant and beautiful place to spend their free time	vs 74% of respondents in the control group
49% agree that such public green areas are well maintained	vs 70% of respondents in the control group
27% report that they do not frequent any public green area	Vs 16% of respondents in the control group
perception of the neighbourhood	
59% agree with the statement that there is a lot of trash and litter on the streets of their neighbourhood	Vs 58% of respondents in the control group
32% think that the air in their neighbourhood is unbreathable	Vs 23% of respondents in the control group
62% agree that the areas they live in are noisy and have heavy traffic	Vs 60% of respondents in the control group
43% agree that the image of the neighbourhood has improved in the past two years	Vs 52% of respondents in the control group
44% agree that the neighbourhood is attractive for tourists.	Vs 38% of respondents in the control group

Physical health and healthy lifestyles

People living or frequenting one of the neighbourhoods listed in Q2 of the survey Intervention Group	The rest of the inhabitants of Nitra Control Group
Healthy habits	
74% rate their physical health to be good, very good, or excellent	Vs 68% of respondents in the control group
44% report engaging in physical exercise at least once a week	vs 55% of respondents in the control group

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43% report spending on average more than one hour a day to prepare their meals at home	Vs 23% of respondents in the control group
24% report consuming at least three portions a day of fruits or vegetables	vs 24% of respondents in the control group
The habit of consuming self-grown fruit and vegetables is widespread among the inhabitants who attend the community centre of Hidepark and could be extended to other social groups or city areas	
34% declare that access to healthy food in a typical week is not easy, mainly for its cost	Vs 34% of respondents in the control group
Are aware of benefits from urban nature and perceive these benefits as potentially increasing in the next future	
Free time and leisure	
Experience healthy leisure practices like walking in nature, cycling, attendance of parks and green areas, sports practice and community gardening	
Perceive an impoverishment of the quality of their free time in public spaces due to the Covid effects	
67% report devoting one hour or more a day to leisure or personal care	Vs 63% of respondents in the control group
72% report spending at least one hour a day caring for their family	Vs 70% of respondents in the control group
43% report spending at least one hour a day playing with or caring for pets.	Vs 41% of respondents in the control group
28% report using the public green areas of their neighbourhood to do sports once a week or more	vs 30% of respondents in the control group
43% report spending one hour or more a day playing, relaxing or doing sport in public green areas	Vs 35% of respondents in the control group
30% reported spending at least one hour a day in social and recreational public spaces	Vs 32% of respondents in the control group
57% are satisfied with the way they spend their free time	Vs 48% of respondents in the control group
the practice of healthy leisure could be improved with respect to the group of local migrant workers	

Mental health

People living or frequenting one of the neighbourhoods listed in Q2 of the survey Intervention Group	The rest of the inhabitants of Nitra Control Group
Experience comparable levels of overall psychological well-being (mean WHO5 $M = 56.11, SD = 23.84$)	($M = 55.50, SD = 20.03$)
Reported similar levels of mental distress (mean K6 $M = 13.92, SD = 5.44$)	(mean K6 score $M = 14.99, SD = 5.30$)

Economic well-being

People living or frequenting one of the neighbourhoods listed in Q2 of the survey Intervention Group	The rest of the inhabitants of Nitra Control Group
52% are satisfied with their personal financial situation	Vs 53% of respondents in the control group
23% report that their financial condition is not enough or just barely sufficient to satisfy their basic needs	Vs 20% of respondents in the control group
57% Are satisfied with the time and resources they have to manage personal matters	Vs 53% of respondents in the control group
Covid pandemic caused a decrease of the income in the tourist and cultural sector as well as higher job insecurity for immigrant workers in the industrial District.	

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Appendix 11 Transect table used during interactive transect walk

Transect:	Locality:	Activities:	Users:	Elements:	Existing and planned interventions of other initiatives:	Safety:	Accessibility:	Emotions and experiences:

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Appendix 11 Selected results from the co-design process of IN-HABIT Co-design Atelier

LEGEND:

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1 | a place between two forests with low visibility, a potential danger to the people |
| 2 | frequented road crossing |
| 3 | frequented road crossing |

- | |
|----------------|
| Arable land |
| Green areas |
| Buildings |
| Water area |
| Road R1 |
| Corridor route |

Appendix 12 Results of the co-design process for locality 2.1 “Beavers Yard”

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materials

author: Bc. Bódor Ibolya

the most common mobiliar materials

- _zinc-plated steel, stainless steel
- _cast aluminum, aluminum
- _massive, wood - iroko, ipe, bamboo, spruce, oak, teak
- _composit - HPRC- high durability, impermeability, comfortable material
- _recycled plastic
- _metal - neither summer nor winter is not very pleasant for a long time
- _concrete
- _corten
- _HPL - laminate boards
- _LDPE
- _polyethylene, polyurethane
- _massive wood-oak, agate, pine

wood related:

- _cement fiber and cement chipboards
- _from plastic waste - even via a 3D printer
- _organic waste - from leaf fall - Šimon Kern
- _biological material, compostable-mycelium, wood chips, gypsum, oat bran mushrooms, bacteria
- _excess materials from local factories - sustainability
- _chemical plastic recycling
- _bioplast - PLA

heat-treated wood:

- _without chemicals, only heat and steam - THERMO WOOD = substitute for tropical woods
- _ / most often ash and pine - thermal ash, thermal pine / increased durability, resistance, more fragile before treatment, preserves the natural properties of wood, safe for the environment, possible recycling

from plastic waste

from leaf fall

thermowood

as

availability of materials

author: Bc. Bódor Ibolya

MATERIAL	PRICE	SUPPLIER:				
metal						
closed square profiles	<table border="1"> <tr> <td> <p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 32,31 € (+10%)</p> </td> <td> <p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 190,49 € (+10%)</p> </td> <td> <p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 9,17 € (+10%)</p> </td> <td> <p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 3,79 € (+10%)</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 32,31 € (+10%)</p>	<p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 190,49 € (+10%)</p>	<p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 9,17 € (+10%)</p>	<p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 3,79 € (+10%)</p>	NR-KOV Vodná 23, Nitra dodáva: KOVIAN s.r.o., 900 61 Gajary
<p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 32,31 € (+10%)</p>	<p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 190,49 € (+10%)</p>	<p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 9,17 € (+10%)</p>	<p>szélesség: 40mm, vastagság: 2mm 8000 db/teker, átlagos szállási tömeg:</p> <p>004 8000000 - 8000 db/teker = 3,79 € (+10%)</p>			
small metal parts		DEK, Nitra				
concrete		AB STAV, Malý Cetin				
C20/25	72 eur / m3					
recycled plastic	- Woodpalstic	Svet Dreva, Nitra				
wood		Pental, Nitra				
planed prisms dry 145x45x100	5,80 eur/ks					
planed dry boards 100x20x2000	4,20 eur/ ks					
wood		PROKOM SR s.r.o., Bratislava Drevoma, Trnava WOODMASTER.SK, Bratislava				
thermal pine 25x100 mm x 3-5,4 m	4,50 eur/ ks 1800 eur/ m3					
thermal pine 19x117x3900mm	12,17 eur/ ks					
thermowood pine 26x115 x 3000 - 5100 mm	54,10 eur/m2					

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promenade
building - variant

pier
art piece

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visualization
promenade

visualization
detail - promenade

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visualization
pier

visualization
detail - pier

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seating
mobiliar

USED MATERIAL

metal
closed square profile 30x30mm
perimeter construction with heels and built-in bicycle stand

wood
form of thermal compression
seat and backrest

VIEW FROM ABOVE

FRONT VIEW

SIDE VIEW

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visualization
detail - seating

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seating
bike path

USED MATERIAL

metal
closed square profile 30x30mm
bench construction

wood
form of heat compression part with a backrest
seating with backrest

VIEW FROM ABOVE

FRONT RIGHT VIEW

LOCATION OF THE QR CODE

author: Bc. Bödör Ibolya

trash bin
mobiliar

VIEW FROM ABOVE

USED MATERIAL

metal
inner container and trash bin carrier

wood
form of thermal compression
circumferential construction of the waste bin

BACK VIEW

SIDE VIEW

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visualization
detail - seating and trash can

cat house
mobiliar

USED MATERIAL

- A recycled old boxes
- B recycled old portable refrigerator
- C recycled old water container

LEGEND
X,Y,Z - [mm] according to the dimensions of the recycled container

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visualization
detail - cat house

Appendix 13 Maps of co-designed hard VIS

ZELOKVET-HIDEPARK-BRIDGE AT VODNA STREET

- 1.1 Near Zelokvet
- 1.2 River bank
- 1.3 Hidepark
- 1.4 Bridge at Vodna street

- 1.1.1 Picnic Meadow
- 1.2.1 Replacement planting of the tree alley: 45-50 trees
- 1.2.2 Lighting
- 1.3.1 Building of sewerage and drinking water supply, sanitary container
- 1.3.2 Revitalization and expansion of community garden
- 1.3.3 Rowboat rental on the Nitra River
- 1.3.4 Food booth - community kitchen
- 1.3.5 DIY Café - community workshop
- 1.3.6 Community bike-sharing station and service
- 1.3.7 Inclusive playground for children
- 1.4.1 Landmark for REMOULD corridor

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BRIDGE ON THE VODNÁ STREET - CITY PARK - PARK BRIDGE

- 2.1 Elementary school Tulipánova
- 2.2 Nitra River surface
- 2.3 City Park - Beaver's Yard
- 2.4 City park

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PARK BRIDGE - UNDERPASS - INDUSTRIAL PARK

- 3.1 The premises of the West Slovak Water Company
- 3.2 Swamp Biotop
- 3.3 Dobrotka Stream Bank
- 3.4 Underpass
- 3.5 Dobrotka Stream Bank
- 3.6 Parking lot - Industrial park
- 3.7 Industrial park

- 3.1.1 Waterworks Garden
- 3.2.1 Restoration and conservation of the natural vegetation system in the swamp habitat
- 3.2.2 Lighting
- 3.3.1 Tree planting
- 3.4.1 Small architecture and art object with the function of a skateboard and pump track
- 3.4.2 Lighting
- 3.5.1 Mobilair for leasure along the cycle path
- 3.6.1 Chill and SmallTalk zone
- 3.7.1 Tree planting - Industrial park

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DRAŽOVCE RESIDENTIAL AREA

- 4.1 Entry to Dražovce
- 4.2 Cultural centre and adjacent areas
- 4.3 Elementary school Dražovce

- 4.1.1 Public picnic zone
- 4.1.2 Lighting
- 4.2.1 Inclusive playground
- 4.2.2 Garden with therapeutic elements
- 4.2.3 Seating mobiliary
- 4.2.4 Mobile marketplace "Dražovisko"
- 4.3.1 Therapeutic and educational garden
- 4.3.2 Multifunctional mobiliary
- 4.3.3 Educational Playground
- 4.3.4 Lighting

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Appendix 14 Detailed descriptions of co-designed hard VIS and plans for their co-deployment and co-management

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.1.	Near Zelokvet
Solutions	1.1.1	Picnic Meadow
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	Establishment of a freely accessible picnic area with barbecue and modular reversible urban mobiliary, additional tree planting. The site will be a freely accessible gathering location for the general public, a place to play outdoor games, and a resting place for cyclists using the cycle path.	
Partners and stakeholders	SUA, City of Nitra, SVP, Botanical Garden, Nitra Volunteer Centre, Nitra Community Foundation, Secondary School of Art Design	
Users and target groups	the general public, cyclists	
Co-deployment	The design of the mobiliary and public barbecues will be implemented in collaboration with SUA FHLE (teachers and students), Secondary School of Art Design with the involvement of the general public and representatives of users and disadvantaged groups. Workshops will be implemented in the community workshop – DIY Café at Hidepark. Involvement of the general public and recruitment of volunteers in the planting of elements and meadow planting will be provided in cooperation with the Nitra Volunteer Centre and the Nitra Community Foundation. Part of the elements of the mobiliary will be procured through standard public procurement and part will be produced at workshops organised in the DIY Café at Hidepark.	
Co-deployment – timeline	Design process 04-05/2022, technical documentation preparation 06-10/2022, procurement of plant material 08-09/2022, collection of meadow material 09-10/2022, planting trees and meadow 10-11/2022, urban mobiliary installation/terrain modulation 2023	
Co-management	Elements of the Picnic Meadow will be managed by the City of Nitra. The Department of Administration and Maintenance of Public Greenery will take care of the meadow (2 employees in the position of a gardener will be trained by the partners SUA FHLE and Botanical Garden in alternative ways of maintenance of public greenery, oatmeal meadows, floating flower beds, experimental flower beds and ecologically protected habitats). Mobiliary and barbecue will be under the management of the Department of Management and Maintenance of Urban Mobiliary and Service Activities.	

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.2	River bank
Solutions	1.2.1	Replacement planting of the tree alley: 45-50 trees

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Innovations	
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The re-planting of the recently cut down poplar alley will be realized on the basis of the recommended assortments from the Department of Environment of the city of Nitra: poplar, oak, beech, ash, hornbeam, maple, rowan, linden. Crown shape: slender, columnar, pyramidal. Seedling stem at planting: minimum 10-12cm. Stabilized by a wooden perpendicularly driven fixed stake, fitted with a tie, protective rubber at the bottom against mechanical damage. The site will be freely accessible to the general public, cyclists.
Partners and stakeholders	SVP, City of Nitra, NGO TRIPTYCH (Hidepark), SUA, NGO Cuketa
Users and target groups	the general public, visitors of Hidepark, elementary schools: Tulipánová, Dražovce
Co-deployment	Terrain clearing and preparatory work on the excavation of the beds will be provided by the SVP, the placement of trees in the root beds and the measure with stabilization stakes will be carried out in the form of a workshop with educational elements with the public and students of the SUA, pupils of the elementary schools Dražovce and Tulipánová under the supervision of teachers of the FHLE and staff of the Botanical Garden. The City of Nitra will provide watering and maintenance after planting. The demarcation plan will be created in cooperation with the SVP, the Environmental Department of the City of Nitra with the participation of the teachers and FHLE students.
Co-deployment – timeline	Preparation of the delineation plan: 3/2022 - 9/2022; Landscaping and preparation of the terrain, marking out and preparation of beds: 9/2022 - 10/2022; Planting: 10/2022 - 11/2022; Procurement of materials: 8/2022 - 10/2022
Co-management	Management will be provided by the City of Nitra - watering, replenishment of fallen plantings in cooperation with SUA and SVP

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.3	Hidepark
Solutions	1.3.1	Building of sewerage and drinking water supply, sanitary container
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	For the location of Hidepark Nitra, a sewerage system and a drinking water access will be built, which will enable the development of activities and ensure the improvement of hygienic conditions for the operation of a community workshop – DIY Café, a mobile community kitchen and the implementation of cultural, social, educational and other activities. The improvement of sanitary	

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	conditions will have a positive impact on visitors of cultural and social centre Hidepark, cyclists and other users of the cycling corridor.
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, City of Nitra, SVP
Users and target groups	Visitors of Hidepark, cyclists, the general public
Co-deployment	The implementation process will be carried out in the form of public procurement, the sanitary container element itself will be further designed in collaboration with the general public during a design workshop from waste materials, the roof of the element will be complemented by a green roof solution and a solar panel. It will be sensitively integrated into the environment of Hidepark spaces.
Co-deployment – timeline	10/2022 - 12/2022 Preparation of technical documentation, 01-03/2022 procurement of a contractor, 4/2023 - 5/2023 realization
Co-management	Management and maintenance will be the responsibility of the HIDEpark partner, primarily representing water and sewage costs and regular maintenance.
Comments	Necessary to be built prior to co-deployment of other solutions at this location

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.3	Hidepark
Solutions	1.3.2	Revitalization and expansion of community garden
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>Creation of pedestrian communications between individual plots, revitalization and delimitation of plots, leisure furniture (10 multifunctional benches with functions: leisure, socialization, demarcation of plots, storage space for tools, aesthetization of space, landmark points in the garden), frames for shading and attachment of protective surfaces for selected plots, frames for trailing plants, information boards and educational elements on plant care, supplemented by QR codes with a link to the Online IN-HUB platform. Sanitary cutting of overgrown and invasive trees in the leisure part of the garden, followed by addition of long-lived fruit trees (traditional varieties of the Nitra region). Hornbeam hedge protective planting between the existing area of the cyclopumptrack and the community garden. Construction of a barbecue in the leisure area (traditional clay oven) and work tables for processing crops grown in the garden. Revitalization of an existing pond - utilizing upcycling and recycling design. Construction of 2 fruit and vegetable dryers. Construction of 1 gazebo and storage space for tools with extensive green roof, side panels with frames for climbing plants, with rainwater drainage and collection system, 3 rainwater collection containers. An online specialist library providing educational materials on organic farming, crop processing methods and cookbooks, linked to the Slovak Agricultural Library. The</p>	

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	garden relaxation area includes an experimental therapeutic garden as a link between leisure and educational activities. Elements of the experimental garden: experimental beds with an irrigation system connected to the rainwater collection and retention system, plantings of herbs, ornamental plants and annuals. Planting plans will be created in cooperation with the Botanical Garden, Faculty of Horticulture and Landscape Architecture, Civic Association Cuketa, students and the public. Once built, it will serve as an educational space for primary and secondary schools.
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, SUA, NGO Cuketa, Botanical Garden, schools
Users and target groups	gardeners, visitors to Hidepark, the general public, schools, residents of Dražovce, partner NGOs in the city of Nitra, Nitra City
Co-deployment	Geometric survey and scanning of the garden space, creation of a digital model of the garden. Pedestrian trails in the garden - terrain preparation, weeding and barking, sanitary cutting, construction of shading frames: organised by Hidepark and Cuketa through a public open call for gardeners involved in the community garden and volunteers. Extensive roof creation, construction of clay grill and benches - organised in a public workshop form under the supervision of experts and teachers at SUA and the Botanical Garden. Gazebo and dryers, storage facilities, containers for rainwater harvesting, frames for trailing plants in the gazebo built by reconstructing adjacent dilapidated shed. Information boards, educational elements, online library deployed in cooperation with Cuketa, Botanical Garden, Faculty of Horticulture and Landscape Engineering and Slovak Agricultural Library. All elements procured and built with regard to the principles of natural building principles.
Co-deployment – timeline	2/2022 - 5/2022: design process of experimental therapeutic flower beds, revitalization of community garden and extension of community garden; 5/2022 - 9/2022: sanitary cutting, clearing of areas for the creation of a new community garden, experimental therapeutic beds 400 m2, laying of sidewalks, planting of an experimental therapeutic garden, planting of shading long-lived woody plants; 4/2023 - 10/2023 revitalization of elements of small architecture and furniture; 2/2023 - 4/2023 preparation and launch of online library, information and educational elements
Co-management	Maintenance of the community garden is the responsibility of the community of gardeners that use it. Co-management of the entire process will be led by Hidepark (LCA - Janka Popovicsová) and NGO Cuketa. Maintenance costs will be partially covered by a symbolic "plot rent" of 5 euros per month per plot.

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.3	Hidepark
Solutions	1.3.3	Rowboat rental on the Nitra River
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	Establishment of rowboat rental requires the construction of a staircase anchored in the body of the river bank that lead to the river level and storage areas that will allow the operation of the activity for the general public. The storage areas will consist of one shipping container, the staircase building will be preceded by safety consultations, and the staff will be trained to ensure the	

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	operation. The rental shop will be equipped with kayaks/rowboats, life jackets, safety helmets and other relevant materials. Online reservation system will be established.
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, SVP, ADOREAL, s.r.o.
Users and target groups	Hidepark visitors, the general public, schools, residents of Dražovce, the city of Nitra
Co-deployment	The entrance staircase to the river surface will be designed and consulted with the SVP, the Office of the Chief Architect of the city of Nitra and the Department of Environment of the city of Nitra. The provision of the storage, rowboats and the staircase will be provided by the external partner company ADOREAL s.r.o. , which will also help co-manage the operation of the rowboat rental.
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2023 - 4/2023: construction and anchoring of stairs to the river bank, fitting of a storage container, equipment of the container, 05/2023 - 09/2023: functional operation
Co-management	ADOREAL, s.r.o. (external partner) will provide the rowboats, container and anchoring the staircase, IN-HABIT partners will provide help with designing the staircase and the storage spaces, online reservation system, co-organization of sports activities and promotion

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.3	Hidepark
Solutions	1.3.4	Food Booth - community kitchen
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The facilities of the community kitchen will meet the hygiene requirements for the sale of food. The space requires a connection to water, electricity and a separate aggregate, the ability to be moved along the entire designed route with the possibility of driven along transport connections in the city. The kitchen will be supplied with worktops, storage cupboards, electric hob, electric heating, fridge, sink and electric coffee machine. Folding furniture, tables and chairs, shading elements, sitting furniture are important equipment. By its design, the community kitchen is compatible with reversible modular furnishing elements of the REMOULD concept, in such a way that together they can create additional functional space or provide additional functions (e.g. a stage for bigger events).	
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, Cuketa NGO, District NGO, HIDEpump NGO, Private School of Art Design, SUA	
Users and target groups	visitors of Hidepark, the general public, schools, inhabitants of Dražovce, civic associations in Nitra, city of Nitra	
Co-deployment	The base structure of the community kitchen element and interior fittings will be procured in public procurement procedure. The cladding and design of the element will be designed following the design of the community workshop through public workshops and volunteering events, with the involvement of NGO Cuketa, NGO District, NGO HidePump and the Private School of Art Design under the guidance of SUA experts.	

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Co-deployment – timeline	2/2023 - 6/2023: Preparation of public procurement. 6/2023 - 7/2023: Acquisition of community kitchen elements, purchase of kitchen equipment, 7/2023 - opening of community kitchen
Co-management	The community kitchen will be managed by the HIDE partner, with community activators (LCA Janka Popovicsová and LCA Sandra Šubertová) in charge of communication with users. The community kitchen, since it will be mobile and transportable, will be used not only in the Hidepark site but in the whole pilot area, as well as for dissemination and replication activities in other parts of Nitra. It will also be provided for rent to other organizations, schools, non-profit organizations, etc.

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.3	Hidepark
Solutions	1.3.5	DIY Café - community workshop
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The structure and equipment of the community workshop must meet the safety conditions for the handling of tools. The space requires a connection to water, electricity and a separate generator. A worktop, storage cabinets and electric heating are essential. An important part of the equipment is folding work furniture, tables and chairs, working equipment, shading elements, sitting furniture. Woodworking tools, metalworking tools, tools for work with fabrics and art tools will also be provided along with a kiln with a shredder for processing waste plastics. The workshop will also serve as a Library of Things, photo chamber, etc.	
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, SUA, NGO I care, Creative centre Nitra, NGO Cuketa, Sekáč - local business, Independent atelier 37, Private Art school of Design	
Users and target groups	Visitors of Hidepark, the general public, schools, inhabitants of Dražovce, civic associations in Nitra, city of Nitra, Creative centre Nitra, Creative centre SUA, disadvantaged groups	
Co-deployment	The construction of the community workshop base structure will be procured through a public procurement process. The building will be adapted for use as a community workshop by the community of active people in the Hidepark. The equipment of the community workshop will be partly procured and partly equipped in cooperation with the collaborating organisations and members of the IN-HUB. Civic association I care will provide an oven with a shredder for plastic processing and associated educational workshops, Independent Atelier 37 will operate a photo chamber and associated workshops and educational activities, NGO Cuketa will provide workshops on the production of educational materials by recycling. The Private School of Art Design will use the workshop for the practical implementation of term and final theses of their students. Sekáč will collaborate in the creation of an outreach concept for garment waste processing and sustainable fashion.	
Co-deployment – timeline	10/2022: Preparation of public procurement. 10/2022 - 12/2022: Acquisition of workshop element, purchase of working equipment, 4/2023 - 5/2023: opening of community workshop	

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Co-management	The community workshop will be managed by the partner HIDE, and the community activators (LCA Janka Popovicsová and LCA Sandra Šubertová) will be in charge of communication with the users. It will also be made available for rent to other organizations, schools, non-profit organizations, etc. At this stage, a cooperation has been agreed with the partner Creative Centre Nitra (an incubator and accelerator in the field of cultural and creative industries with a presence in the city of Nitra and beyond), which will use the premises of the DIY Café for the organisation of CCI Labs. After the end of the IN-HABIT project, partners are considering to include the DIY Café as an off-site location of the Creative Centre focused on community-oriented activities.
Comments	DIY Café is expected to be used for participatory based co-deployment of several other solutions along the corridor, thus it should be deployed prior to other solutions.

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.3	Hidepark
Solutions	1.3.6	Community bike-sharing station and service
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	In the first phase, the community bikesharing will consist of 14 bicycles that are assembled from old retro bikes, repaired, painted the same colour and completed with basic elements (bell, lighting, lock). The bikes will be loaned out for period of 4 months (February to May, June to September, October to January), with bike servicing primarily provided in the summer at the community bike shop, along with workshops on bike maintenance and minor repairs.	
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, NGO HIDEPump, NGO Lets cycle Nitra	
Users and target groups	the general public, cyclists, students, low-income families	
Co-deployment	There is an existing community bike shop at Hidepark (since 2017) that is currently unused. BikeSharing will begin operating a bike rental and maintenance service here, which will be expanded in summer of 2021 to include workshops for the public on bike repair and maintenance. The BikeSharing and bike servicing service will run all year round, with workshops running primarily in the summer months each year.	
Co-deployment – timeline	2/2022 - 5/2022: Reservation cycle "summer semester" 6/2022 - 8/2022: Reservation cycle "summer" 9/2022 - 1/2023: Reservation cycle "winter semester" 2/2023 - 5/2023: Reservation cycle "summer semester" 6/2023 - 8/2023: Reservation cycle "summer" 9/2023 - 1/2024: Reservation cycle "winter semester". 4/2022 - 9/2022 Workshops for bike maintenance and servicing.	
Co-management	Bikesharing will be managed by the partner HIDE, while the communication with users will be handled by community activators (LCA Janka Popovicsová and LCA Sandra Šubertová). The service provided will be accessible to the general public. Workshops on bike repair and maintenance will be done in cooperation with NGO HidePump and NGO Lets cycle Nitra!	

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Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.3	Hidepark
Solutions	1.3.7	Inclusive playground for children
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>The playground space will be created in two phases. The first will be realized in the form of a public workshop with elements made of waste wood. The second phase will be implemented based on suggestions from the user public. In addition to safety and aesthetics, the playground equipment should meet other conditions like principles of inclusion, multisensory experiences and accessibility. The playground elements will be designed for visitors of the Hidepark, the general public, users of the cycle path and people with disabilities</p>	
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, SUA	
Users and target groups	visitors of Hidepark, the general public, schools and kindergartens, civic associations in Nitra, people with disabilities	
Co-deployment	The implementation will be carried out in two phases. The first will take the form of a public workshop made of waste wood material, under strict professional supervision and after consultation with experts. The second will take the form of a public procurement for the playground elements.	
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2022 - 12/2022: Preparation of public workshop and design of playground elements, 10/2022 - 12/2022: Realization of workshops for playground elements production, 3/2023 - 5/2023: selection of playground elements and preparation of public procurement, 6/2023 - 7/2023 installation of playground elements.	
Co-management	The inclusive playground will be managed by the partner HIDE, who will supervise the safety and functionality of the individual elements.	

Zone	1	Zelokvet-Hidepark-Bridge at Vodna street
Locality	1.4	Bridge at Vodna street
Solutions	1.4.1	Landmark for REMOULD corridor
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>An orientation element, informing about the activities that can be carried out in the area with information about the natural and architectural points of interest in the area, already existing and implemented within the IN-HABIT project. Equipped with QR codes, with translations in several languages.</p>	

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Partners and stakeholders	City of Nitra, Department of Maintenance of the City of Nitra, Private Secondary School of Art Design
Users and target groups	the general public, cyclists
Co-deployment	The production of individual elements of the orientation system will be procured according to the completed designs. The designs will be prepared during educational workshops with students of the Private Secondary School of Art Design. The elements will be installed in cooperation with the Department of Maintenance of the city of Nitra
Co-deployment – timeline	10/2023 – 12/2023 design and realization
Co-management	After the co-deployment, the management of the solution will fall under the competency of the city administration.

Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.1	Elementary school Tulipánova
Solutions	2.1.1	Educational therapeutic garden
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>The educational garden for the students of the Tulipánova elementary school will fulfil several functions. In addition to educational purpose, it should also represent a significant aesthetic shift in the area of the elementary school and a place for rest of the students, teachers and their parents. Therapeutic functions of the garden can be used for several types of therapy: art therapy, occupational therapy, psychotherapy. The garden should have a positive biomechanical, sensorimotor, cognitive impact on children and support building of interpersonal relationships.</p>	
Partners and stakeholders	Elementary school Tulipánova, Cuketa NGO, Botanical garden, FHLE SUA	
Users and target groups	students, parents, teachers and visitors to Tulipánová elementary school	
Co-deployment	<p>The preparation of the educational and design workshop will take place in two phases. The workshop in the first phase will be implemented with students of the elementary school, and after the workshop, the results will be evaluated and processed into the design process. The first phase of implementation will take place together with students, teachers, parents and students of FHLE SUA. The second phase, the planting will be carried out with elementary school students, elementary school teachers, parents and FHLE SUA students.</p>	
Co-deployment – timeline	4/2022 – 6/2022 design workshop and design process, 3 - 6/2023 first phase of implementation, 9/2022 - 6/2023 ecological design workshops and design process, 9 - 10/2023 second phase of implementation	
Co-management	The educational therapeutic garden will be handed over to the Tulipánová elementary school after implementation. It will be used mainly by the pupils of the school, parents of pupils and teachers.	

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Comments	The overall design must be consulted with the Environmental Department of the City of Nitra before implementation.
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Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.2	Nitra River surface
Solutions	2.2.1	Artistic object on the river surface on abandoned concrete structures
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	Installation of an art object or group of objects near the river bank in front of the dam area. The object will be installed on unused concrete structures, which are part of the unused, old water compartment of the dam. The work, or group of works, will require secure anchoring on the heels, boreholes and chemical anchors. The overall construction of the work must be resistant to weather conditions. It must be connected to the space on which it will be installed and designed as a site-specific object directly for the selected location.	
Partners and stakeholders	SVP, City of Nitra, District NGO	
Users and target groups	general public	
Co-deployment	The art work will be commissioned on the basis of a winning design in open selection process after a public call for sculptors and artists. The evaluation of the results of the call will be carried out by an expert jury. The creation of the selected work will be provided after consultation with the author of the selected design. The implementation must be checked by the author of the proposal through entire process. The completed art work must be securely installed at a pre-selected location.	
Co-deployment – timeline	1/2023 - 5/2023: creation of a public tender for the design of the art work and creation of the design of the work. 8/2023 - 12/2023: realization and installation of the work	
Co-management	responsibility for the maintenance will be managed by city of Nitra	
Comments	The overall design must be consulted with the Slovak Waterways Company – SVP, Chief Architect of the city and Department of Environment of the City of Nitra prior to implementation	

Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.2	Nitra River surface
Solutions	2.2.2	Floating flower beds - cRAFTS

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Innovations	
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	cRAFTS – floating plant beds are an element that combines the two underused values of Nitra pilot art and environment in the best way. Live islands of phytoremediative plants creating floating land art above the surface, while absorbing heavy metals and providing a nesting place for fish below it, will be installed in one of the most polluted rivers in Slovakia. In addition to aesthetic function, the elements of floating flower beds must meet mainly safety parameters. In the event of detachment from the anchoring site, the bed must be divided into several parts which will not damage the dam and will not be dangerous for the animals living in the river habitat.
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, Botanical garden, Cuketa NGO, SVP, Agrobiotech, Institute of Environmental Management
Users and target groups	broad public, students
Co-deployment	The design of floating flower beds will be implemented in the form of a professional workshop in cooperation with FHLE SUA, the Botanical Garden, the Institute of Environmental Management and Agrobiotech. The implementation of the results of the design process will be publicly procured. The realization itself will be thoroughly documented and implemented as part of the educational process for FHLE SUA students.
Co-deployment – timeline	10/2022 - 3/2023 preparation of the design of the floating flowerbed, 4/2023 public procurement, 4/2023 - 7/2023 realization
Co-management	The professional care of the floating beds after implementation will be taken over by the Department of Environment of the city of Nitra and its professionally trained employees in the position of a gardener.

Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.3	City Park - Beaver's Yard
Solutions	2.3.1	Pier and mobiliary
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The installation of the pier, multifunctional mobiliary and cat shelters in the area near the dead arm of the river was designed by FHLE SUA students on the basis of suggestions from the IN-HUB. The design must undergo technical processing with a static assessment before the start of the implementation process. The implementation itself must be consulted with the Department of the Environment and the Department of the Chief Architect of the City of Nitra. The whole implementation process must take place under strict security supervision. The design of the furniture is suitable for overcoming communication barriers of people with physical disabilities.	

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	The interventions planned in the area will be carried out with regard to the natural habitat of the European beaver.
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, NGO DISTRICT, City of Nitra, Diocese of Nitra
Users and target groups	broad public, visitors of the city park, schools, kindergartens
Co-deployment	Procurement of production and preparation of technical documentation are the main tasks before the actual implementation of the pier and mobiliary. The production process will take place under professional safety and design supervision. FHLE SUA students will also volunteer to carry out the implementation.
Co-deployment – timeline	The design process of individual elements took place in 2021, 3/2023 - 5/2023 procurement and preparation of technical documentation for furniture and piers, 5/2023 - 7/2023 production of furniture and piers, 8/2023 installation of elements.
Co-management	The responsibility for the pier and the furniture and its maintenance will be taken over by the City of Nitra.
Comments	All VIS planned in this locality has to undergo additional compliance check with newly obtained EU structural funds project of revitalisation of the Old City Park in February 2022.

Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.3	City Park - Beaver's Yard
Solutions	2.3.2	Green interventions
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The area around the dead arm of the river will be cleaned of airborne trees, trusses and dangerous trees damaged by European beaver population. The space will then be supplemented with the planting of long-lived woody plants, flowering trusses and trailing plants as shade-like undergrowth under the woody plants. The planting will take place in the form of public brigades in cooperation with Tulipánová Elementary School, FHLE SUA and the Botanical Garden. The space will be aestheticized and cultivated for the general public and elementary school students.	
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, City of Nitra, Diocese of Nitra, Botanical garden, Tulipánova Elementary School	
Users and target groups	general public, visitors of the city park, schools, kindergartens	
Co-deployment	The implementation of safety cutting will take place in cooperation with the Department of Environment (City of Nitra), volunteers and FHLE SUA students under the supervision of experts from the Botanical Garden. The public, students from FHLE and students of Tulipánova primary school will be involved in the planting of plant material.	

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Co-deployment – timeline	9/2022 realization of hygienic cuttings, 9/2022 - 10/2023 planting of trees and trusses
Co-management	Professional care of green plantings (interventions) after planting will be carried out by the Department of Environment of the city of Nitra and its professionally trained employees in the position of a gardener.
Comments	All VIS planned in this locality has to undergo additional compliance check with newly obtained EU structural funds project of revitalisation of the Old City Park in February 2022.

Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.3	City Park - Beaver's Yard
Solutions	2.3.3	Innovative educational elements
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>We plan to supplement the area of the natural habitat of the beaver population near the dead branch of the Nitra River with informative and educational boards with interactive play elements. These must be built with great emphasis on the location, as our interest is not to disturb the natural habitat of the European beaver by the visitors. They will be equipped with QR codes with a link to information and educational materials on the online IN-HUB platform. The space will include educational works of art made from found beaver-eaten trees. A wildlife camera will be installed in the space, from which the stream will be available on the online IN-HUB platform. All elements installed in the area must be consulted with the Department of Environment of the city of Nitra.</p>	
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, District NGO, NGO Cuketa, City of Nitra, Diocese of Nitra, Private Secondary School of Art Design	
Users and target groups	general public, visitors of the city park, schools, kindergartens	
Co-deployment	The design process of the elements will be carried out with a designer, biologist and students from the Private School of Art Design in collaboration with experts on child education and environment. Production of the designed elements will be procured and installation will take place through volunteer brigades with the general public. Artworks from beaver-eaten trees will be created in design workshops.	
Co-deployment – timeline	4/2022- 3/2023 design and preparation of information for interactive information boards 4/2023 consultations of Department of Environment of city of Nitra. 5/2023 - 9/2023 procurement and building of objects, installation.	
Co-management	Responsibility for the educational elements and their maintenance will be managed by the City of Nitra.	
Comments	All VIS planned in this locality has to undergo additional compliance check with newly obtained EU structural funds project of revitalisation of the Old City Park in February 2022.	

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Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.4	City Park
Solutions	2.4.1	Bicycles for people with disabilities
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>Providing bicycles respectful of specific needs of disabled city residents, visitors and children. The plan is to add two special bicycles for residents and with disabilities to Arriva's existing urban bikesharing system. To better adapt to the specific needs of the users, the individual parts of the bikes should be adjustable. These bicycles will be manufactured by a certified company with a specification for this kind of professional production.</p>	
Partners and stakeholders	Arriva	
Users and target groups	people with disabilities, children and visitors of Nitra	
Co-deployment	<p>As the selected bicycles respect the specific needs of residents with disabilities and visitors of the city, their selection will be professionally consulted and procured on the basis of the recommended functionalities and technical specifications. They will be installed in Arriva's bikesharing racks, which will take responsibility for their care and operation once they are in place.</p>	
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2023- 6/2023 public procurement and start of bikesharing	
Co-management	<p>Arriva company will become a partner that will be included in the bike selection process from the start. Once procured, they will take over the maintenance of these bikes, fit them with their specific localization software and place them in their rack in the city park. Company will be in charge of the complete operation and maintenance.</p>	

Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.4	City Park
Solutions	2.4.2	Public mobile sauna
Innovations		

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Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The main requirement for the public sauna element is that it can be moved along the whole route. The sauna will be a small architectural element made of wood or other eco-friendly or waste materials. It will be installed on a steel chassis and stabilisable wheels. It will also be a visual art object in public space. The minimum capacity will be 4 users. The sauna will operate on the principle of online booking.
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, City of Nitra, NGO Icebears
Users and target groups	the general public, fishermen and members of NGO Icebears
Co-deployment	The creation of the conceptual design and user concept will be carried out in interdisciplinary setting between the architect and the designer in consultation with the members of the NGO Icebears. Regular quality checks of the production by the authors will be carried out throughout the production process. The production of the object will be procured. Subsequently, an online booking system will be created for the public.
Co-deployment – timeline	9/2022 - 11/2022: Creation of conceptual and functional design in cooperation with architect. 11/2022 Public contest for technical documentation and production of object, 11/2022 - 12/2022 Production of object. 1/2023 Installation of sauna and opening during the Ice Bears Festival
Co-management	The sauna on wheels will be taken over by the NGO IceBears, which will be responsible for the operation and maintenance of the sauna along with the operation of the reservation system.

Zone	2	Bridge on the Vodná street - City Park - Park Bridge
Locality	2.4	City Park
Solutions	2.4.3	Installation of elements from poplar trunks
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The functional-spatial design of the poplar trunk elements will be the result of a participatory design process. In this case, it is the character and identity of the material that is important, not its future use. The poplar trunks are fragments of the former iconic tree avenue of the city of Nitra with great sentimental value for local residence, which was cut down after the first year of the project. The felling of 180 monumental black poplar trees, negatively impacted the general public of the city and had a degenerating effect on the overall aesthetics of the route.	
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, City of Nitra	
Users and target groups	the general public, visitors of Nitra, elementary schools Dražovce and Tulipánová	
Co-deployment	The design process of the elements created from poplar trunks will be supervised by a designer and a structural engineer. Children from elementary schools will be involved in the design process and their outputs from art workshops can serve as inspiration for the designer. The proposed design must pass the approval of the structural engineer. Based on the resulting design, the production and installation of the elements will be completed.	
Co-deployment – timeline	4/2023 - 6/2023 art workshop with pupils from primary schools, design process and structural control, 7/2023 - 8/2023 - procurement of production and installation; production and installation	

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Co-management	Responsibility for maintenance and safety of the objects will be taken over by the Nitra City.
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Zone	3	Park bridge - Underpass - Industrial park
Locality	3.1	The premises of the West Slovak Water Company
Solutions	3.1.1	Waterworks Garden
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>The design of the waterworks garden area will serve as a basis for the realization of a rest area from the overgrown unvisited grove along the Dobrotka Stream. In the design process, rest areas with mobiliary, paved pedestrian roads, water play and educational elements will be designed. An important element of the design will be planting of native plant assortments for the water areas and surrounding aquatic habitats. The design will respond to the recreational needs of the general public as well as the interactive, educational and play needs of the kindergartens and elementary schools.</p>	
Partners and stakeholders	West Slovak Water Company, City of Nitra, FHLE SUA, Botanical garden	
Users and target groups	general public, schools, kindergartens, employees of West Slovak Water Company	
Co-deployment	The design process of the water garden will start after a thorough inspection of the allocated area together with all the partners involved. The design process will involve teachers from FHLE SUA, experts from the Botanical Garden and students from FHLE. After the dendrological survey, safety felling and clearing of the area will be carried out	
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2023 thorough inspection of the area with dendrologist and partners involved in preparation process, 4/2023 - 9/2023 creation of design and technical documentation, 4/2023 - 7/2023 clearing of dangerous and woody growth	
Co-management	FHLE SUA will be responsible for the quality and feasibility of the design process, the responsibility for the implementation and subsequent maintenance of the space will be assumed by the West Slovak Water Company in consultation with FHLE SUA.	

Zone	3	Park bridge - Underpass - Industrial park
Locality	3.2	Swamp Biotope
Solutions	3.2.1	Restoration and conservation of the natural vegetation system in the swamp habitat
Innovations		

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Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	In the area of the natural swamp biotope near the Dobrotka stream we plan to install informative and educational boards with interactive play elements. These must be installed with great attention to the site so that they do not interfere with or tempt visitors to disturb the habitat. The material chosen for the creation of the information and education elements must be strong and wood cannot be used in the area, due to the high probability of rapid decay. The element will be connected to a seating area. All elements installed in the space must be consulted with the Department of the Environment of the City of Nitra and West Slovak Water Company.
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, NGO District, NGO Cuketa, City of Nitra, West Slovak Water Company
Users and target groups	the general public, visitors of city park, schools, kindergartens
Co-deployment	Implementation of restoration of the swamp habitat area will require professional ecological consultation. The creation of this space will be documented and developed as a publicly available educational document that will be updated throughout the duration of the project.
Co-deployment – timeline	4/ 2022- 3/2023 Creation of design and preparation of information for interactive informative boards 4/2023 Consultation at Department of Environment of Nitra City 5/2023 - 9/2023 Installation in space.
Co-management	The management and maintenance of the swamp will be carried out together with the Water Garden by the West Slovak Water Company.

Zone	3	Park bridge - Underpass - Industrial park
Locality	3.3	Dobrotka stream bank
Solutions	3.3.1	Tree planting
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The planting of 70 trees along the Dobrotka river stream will fulfil the visual function of an optical wall separating the natural landscape from the D2 expressway. At the same time, they will serve as windbreaks and create space for habitat development. The expected assortments of trees will be selected from traditional fruit and ornamental tree species in consultation with a dendrologist.	
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, NGO Let's cycle Nitra, City of Nitra, Nitra Volunteer Centre	
Users and target groups	the general public, residents and visitors of the city of Nitra, cyclists, inhabitants of Dražovce, employees of Jaguar Land Rover	
Co-deployment	In the first phase, the cleaning of the terrain and preparatory work on the excavation of the beds, which will be procured. Rooting of the trees and stabilization measures will be carried out with Jaguar Land Rover staff and volunteers from the general public in cooperation with the Nitra Volunteer Centre. The demarcation plan will be created in cooperation with the Department of the Environment of the City of Nitra with the participation of FHLE SUA teachers and students.	
Co-deployment – timeline	Preparation of demarcation plan: 3/2022 - 10/2022; Landscaping, demarcation and bed preparation: 10/2022; Procurement of material: 9/2022 - 10/2022; Planting: 10/2022 - 11/2022;	

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Co-management	The management will be provided by the City of Nitra - watering, replenishment of plantings in cooperation with SUA and Slovak Water Management Company.
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Zone	3	Park bridge - Underpass - Industrial park
Locality	3.4	Underpass
Solutions	3.4.1	Small architecture and art object with the function of a skateboard and pump track
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The area under the R1 highway bridge will be reclaimed by improving the surface of the crossing under the bridge, creating a structure that will be shaped as part of the skateboard and pumptrack block. The spatial solution of the space under the underpass and its surroundings requires the creation of a high-quality design-architectural proposal and technical documentation. The individual elements of the solution must be sufficiently strong and resistant to manual damage and flooding from the nearby Dobrotka stream.	
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, NGO Lets cycle Nitra, City of Nitra, Nitra Volunteer organization	
Users and target groups	the general public, cyclists, inhabitants of Dražovce, employees of JLR	
Co-deployment	After the design solution is developed, the underpass site in the Dobrotka stream environment must be landscaped and the crossing area raised above the level of the stream that flows through the underpass. Subsequently, the individual elements serving the normal crossing and the pumptrack and other parts of the runway can be installed. The active parts of the space will be complemented by visual and lighting solutions. Based on the design, an implementation plan will be developed.	
Co-deployment – timeline	9/2022 - 1/2023 - Creation of design and technical documentation. 2/2023 - Realization plan. 3/2023 - 5/2023 Production of solution elements. 6/2023 - 9/2023 Installation of elements of pumptrack and installation of visual and light solutions.	
Co-management	Management will be provided by the City of Nitra and SVP	

Zone	3	Park bridge - Underpass - Industrial park
Locality	3.5	Dobrotka Stream Bank
Solutions	3.5.1	Mobiliary for leisure along the cycle path
Innovations		

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Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	Separately placed multifunctional seating elements installed on the bank of the Dobrotka stream near the cycle path. We will put emphasis on the location of mobiliary and the nature of the design must be in accordance with the surrounding landscape.
Partners and stakeholders	FHLE SUA, City of Nitra, Slovak Water Management Company, Municipal Services Nitra
Users and target groups	broad public, visitors to the city, residents of Dražovce, schools, employees in the industrial park, visitors to the cycle path
Co-deployment	The designed and selected mobiliary will be procured with regard to the ecological dimension of the material used. We will install it in cooperation with the Municipal Services of the City of Nitra.
Co-deployment – timeline	6/2022 - 12/2022 design or selection of sitting mobiliary, 1/2023 - 7/2023 public procurement, 8/2023 - 10/2023 realization and installation of sitting mobiliary
Co-management	The maintenance will be provided by the City of Nitra.

Zone	3	Park bridge - Underpass - Industrial park
Locality	3.6	Parking lot - Industrial park
Solutions	3.6.1	Chill and SmallTalk zone
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	Making the parking area in the industrial park in front of the Jaguar Land Rover production facilities more pleasant place. The allocation of 5 parking spaces in the parking lot area will create space for the implementation of an element of an elevated flowerbed intended for planting drought-loving woody plants. It will be supplemented by a solution for sitting and rest as part of the flowerbed construction together with the ashtrays.	
Partners and stakeholders	Jaguar Land Rover, FHLE SUA Agrobiotech	
Users and target groups	Employees of Jaguar Land Rover	
Co-deployment	In the area of five parking spaces, multifunctional elevated flower beds with irrigation and insulation solutions will be designed, together with mostly drought-free plantings. The implementation itself will be procured and implemented according to the created technical documentation. We will build the flower beds with the help of Jaguar Land Rover employees under the supervision of teachers and experts from FHLE SUA and Agrobiotech.	
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2023 - 7/2023 design of raised flowerbed, public procurement, 8/2023 - 10/2023 realization and planting of flowerbeds with areas for rest; 10/2022 - 11/2022 tree planting	
Co-management	The care of the plant assortment, condition and any maintenance of the planting beds and seating areas will be provided by Jaguar Landrover.	

Zone	3	Park bridge - Underpass - Industrial park
Locality	3.7	Industrial park

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Solutions	3.7.1	Tree planting - Industrial park
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The planting of 70 pieces of trees in industrial park.	
Partners and stakeholders	JLR, FHLE SUA	
Users and target groups	employees of JLR	
Co-deployment	Terrain clearance and preparatory works for the excavation of the beds will be provided by Jaguar Land Rover. The placement of the trees in the root beds and the provision of stabilisation stakes will also be undertaken by Jaguar Land Rover. The demarcation plan will be drawn up in cooperation with the Department of Environment of the City of Nitra with the participation of teachers from the FHLE students.	
Co-deployment – timeline	Preparation of the demarcation plan: 3/2023 - 5/2023; Preparation of the terrain, excavation of the beds: 6/2023 - 8/2023; Planting: 9/2023 - 10/2023; Procurement of materials: 3/2023 - 4/2023	
Co-management	The care of the trees from the implemented planting will be provided by JRL.	

Zone	4	Dražovce residential area
Locality	4.1	Entry to Dražovce
Solutions	4.1.1	Public picnic zone
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The picnic area will be created near the Dobrotka stream leading to the residential area of Dražovce. The area will be populated with long-lived trees, supplemented by grass planting, perennial planting and oat meadow natural for this habitat. Planting of trees, the perennial plantings and meadows will be run in cooperation with FHLE SUA and the Botanical Garden in Nitra. An important element of the area will be the public grill and a fire pit with the appropriate sitting mobiliary with bicycle racks and trash bins. Volunteers from the Nitra Volunteer Center, broad public and the Dražovce neighbourhood will be involved in the implementation process in cooperation with the Dražovce elementary school. The picnic meadow will serve the inhabitants of the Dražovce neighbourhood and passing cyclists.	
Partners and stakeholders	City of Nitra, Nitra Volunteer Centre, Dražovce elementary school	
Users and target groups	inhabitants of Dražovce, visitors, cyclists, schools, kindergartens	

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Co-deployment	A public workshop will be held prior to the actual design process. Planting must be carried out under professional supervision according to the design ranges in the General urban greenery plan. The area around the fire pit and grill must be safety landscaped to prevent accidental spread of fire and must not be located under any trees or in close proximity to shrubs or grass beds. The fire pit and grill shall be constructed of solid, natural materials, supporting the idea of ecological design. Their appearance must be designed by or in consultation with a designer or landscape architect. Planting of plant material should be done through volunteer activities. The installation of the grill, fire pit and furnishings will either be procured or created by volunteer groups under professional guidance based on the proposed technical documentation.
Co-deployment – timeline	5/2022 - 9/2022: Preparation of public workshop and design of furnishing elements and special-compositional solutions. 7/2022 - 10/2022: Preparation of technical documentation and procurement of elements. 10/2022 - 8/2023: Realization of workshops for furnishing elements production, procurement of hard-producing elements, preparations of terrain, planting, installation of community grill.
Co-management	The management of the picnic area will be carried out in cooperation with the City of Nitra, MH Invest, NGO Pomáhajko, NGO Pre Dražovce

Zone	4	Dražovce residential area
Locality	4.2	Cultural centre and adjacent areas
Solutions	4.2.1	Inclusive playground
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The design of an inclusive playground must be designed with the specific needs of the users in combination with the needs of the general public. In addition to safety, playground equipment should meet other conditions, namely the principles of inclusion, multi-sensory experiences and accessibility and resistance to vandalism. The overall design should be subject not only to function but also to the aesthetic needs of the surrounding environment.	
Partners and stakeholders	NGO Pomáhajko, City of Nitra, FHLE SUA, Nitra Volunteer Centre	
Users and target groups	inhabitants and visitors of Dražovce, general public, visitors of cultural centre Dražovce, Dražovce Elementary school	
Co-deployment	The implementation will be carried out in two phases. The first will take the form of a public design workshop and refinement of the designs by experts through a public call for designers in consultation with experts in specific physiological needs and therapists. The first design phase will continue with the procurement of some of the playground and recreation elements and their installation. The second phase will be a continuation of the public workshop and subsequent procurement of playground elements and installation volunteer activities with the involvement of the general public, residents of Dražovce and with volunteers from Nitra Volunteer Centre.	

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Co-deployment – timeline	3/2022 - 10/2022: Preparation of public workshop and design of playground elements, 10/2022 - 12/2022: Realization of workshops on production of playground elements. 1/2023 - 4/2023: Selection of playground elements and preparation of public procurement. 4/2022 - 5/2022 Installation of playground elements.
Co-management	Management of inclusive playground will be realized in cooperation between City of Nitra and NGO Pomáhajko.

Zone	4	Dražovce residential area
Locality	4.2	Cultural centre and adjacent areas
Solutions	4.2.2	Garden with therapeutic elements
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The therapeutic-educational garden has a calming effect on the psyche of the users based on the colour and size composition of the perennial and annuals planting beds and naturally supports the insect habitat around the beds. It will also contain herbal elements with medicinal benefits, food uses and use in natural cosmetics. The beds will be designed in such a way that they are tactilely accessible for people with mobility problems. The therapeutic functions of the garden can be used for other types of therapies such as art therapy, occupational therapy, psychotherapy. The garden improves biomechanical, sensorimotor, cognitive, interpersonal and other qualities.	
Partners and stakeholders	City of Nitra, association of gardeners	
Users and target groups	Elementary school Dražovce, Cuketa NGO, Botanical garden, FHLE SUA, NGO Pomáhajko	
Co-deployment	The therapeutic garden must be designed together with experts from the botanical garden or in the form of a public call for garden architects, in the form of educational workshops together with the residents of Dražovce, the inhabitants of the city of Nitra and the students of FHLE SUA. Public participation is also foreseen in the implementation. The outputs from the educational workshop will be professionally processed into design and planting plans. The actual implementation will then be carried out in an educational way with the involvement of volunteers, students and residents of Dražovce.	
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2022 - 10/2022 public workshop, completion of a draft by experts and final design, procurement of greenery, 9/2022 - 10/2022 - first phase of realization, 4/2023 - 7/2023 design process and second phase of realization	
Co-management	Management and maintenance of the garden with therapeutic elements will be realized in cooperation between City of Nitra and NGO Pomáhajko.	

Zone	4	Dražovce residential area
Locality	4.2	Cultural centre and adjacent areas

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Solutions	4.2.3	Seating mobiliary
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	Multifunctional mobiliary will complement the surroundings of the Community centre in Dražovce. Due to the high level of vandalism, the designed furniture must be extremely strong and resistant to damage. The ability to create your own compositions from individual pieces of the furniture will allow the community to use it for a wide range of outdoor community and individual activities.	
Partners and stakeholders	City of Nitra, association of gardeners	
Users and target groups	residents of Dražovce, local NGOs, people with disabilities	
Co-deployment	The design process, which will decide on the functions of the furniture, will take place during joint workshops with the inhabitants of Dražovce and in the form of a public call for designers in cooperation with FHLE. The design and procurement must be carried out with an emphasis on the durability and strength of the furniture.	
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2022 - 10/2022 selection and design of seating mobiliary, procurement of mobiliary, 4/2023 - 6/2023 - installation of mobiliary	
Co-management	Responsibility and maintenance for the seating furniture will be taken over by the City of Nitra in cooperation with the NGO Pomáhajko	

Zone	4	Dražovce residential area
Locality	4.2	Cultural centre and adjacent areas
Solutions	4.2.4	Mobile marketplace "Dražovisko"
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	Elements of the mobile marketplace should be robust, resistant to damage and exterior weather conditions. Their foldability and easy handling are important features. They will mainly be used for the sale of fruit, vegetables, flowers and home-grown produce in the form of yard sales. Aesthetically, they should complement the planned solutions of the mobiliary, inclusive playground and plantings around the Community centre in Dražovce. Their advantage will be their mobility and the possibility of using them at several places along the route.	
Partners and stakeholders	City of Nitra, association of gardeners	
Users and target groups	residents of Dražovce, gardeners, NGO Cuketa, users of the route and organizers of cultural, educational, community and other events in Nitra	
Co-deployment	The design process of the mobile marketplace elements will be carried out with an emphasis on local identity and will be handled by a designer. Based on the design, technical documentation will	

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	be developed. The production of the elements of the marketplace will be procured according to the developed technical documentation.
Co-deployment – timeline	1/2023 - 4/2023 design of elements of reversible market, procurement of elements, 5/2023 - 7/2023 - first phase of realization, 9/2023 - 10/2023 second phase of realization
Co-management	The maintenance and mediation of use of the mobile market will be taken over by the City of Nitra in cooperation with the gardeners' association.

Zone	4	Dražovce residential area
Locality	4.3	Elementary school Dražovce
Solutions	4.3.1	Therapeutic and educational garden
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>The therapeutic-educational garden has a calming effect on the psyche of the users based on the colour and size of the perennial and annuals beds and naturally supports the insect habitat around the beds. Observation of this system will be included in outdoor education as part of the regular curriculum. At the same time, the planting will incorporate herbaceous elements with medicinal benefits, food uses, and use in natural cosmetics. The therapeutic functions of the garden can be used for other therapies such as arterial therapy, occupational therapy, and psychotherapy. The garden improves biomechanical, sensorimotor, cognitive, interpersonal and other areas.</p>	
Partners and stakeholders	elementary school Dražovce, NGO Cuketa, Botanical Garden, SUA, City of Nitra	
Users and target groups	Pupils from elementary school Dražovce, parents and teachers	
Co-deployment	<p>The design process of the educational therapeutic garden will take place in the form of an open call and competition and will be worked on jointly by teachers and students of FHLE SUA, children and teachers from Dražovce School. Some elements of the garden will be implemented together with the parents of the children from Dražovce School and others in cooperation with the Botanical Garden and FHLE SUA. All plants planted in the bed must be safe and, ideally, edible.</p>	
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2022 - 9/2022 Design of spatial solutions, procurement of greenery, 9/2022 - 11/2022 - first phase of realization, 4/2023 - 7/2023 second phase of realization	
Co-management	Responsibility for the care of the plantings will be taken over by the Dražovce Elementary School.	

Zone	4	Dražovce residential area
Locality	4.3	Elementary school Dražovce
Solutions	4.3.2	Multifunctional mobiliary

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Innovations	
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The multifunctional mobiliary will complement the redesign of the selected site in the area of the Dražovce School. Due to the high level of vandalism, the designed furniture must be extremely robust and resistant to damage. The possibility to create their own compositions from individual pieces of the furniture will help the teachers and pupils of the primary school to use it for a wide range of outdoor teaching and for the implementation of leisure, recreation and community activities of the school.
Partners and stakeholders	Elementary school Dražovce, Nitra Volunteer Centre, City of Nitra, SUA
Users and target groups	pupils of Elementary school Dražovce, parents and teachers
Co-deployment	The seating mobiliary will complement the garden and playground in the area of the Dražovce School. Its main characteristics will be safety, reversibility, durability. The design of the overall solution will be created in the form of a public call for proposals in cooperation with the FHLE SUA, or with teachers and students of the FHLE SUA. On the basis of the design and technical documentation, the difficult to produce elements will be procured, the rest will be created during volunteer activities with teachers from the school, parents of children and volunteers from Dražovce and Nitra.
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2022 - 12/2022 selection and design of seating mobiliary, procurement of mobiliary, 4/2023 - 6/2023 - installation of mobiliary
Co-management	Responsibility for the maintenance and any repairs of the mobiliary will be taken over by the Dražovce School.

Zone	4	Dražovce residential area
Locality	4.3	Elementary school Dražovce
Solutions	4.3.3	Educational Playground
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	The educational playground will be a playground with educational and play elements on the theme of fauna, flora and healthy lifestyle. In addition to raising awareness of these topics, the play elements will develop motor skills, fine motor skills, concentration and collective play. An important element is the function and durability of the individual game elements and their varying age and experience levels for the different age levels of children attending the school. The design of the individual elements should correspond with the overall garden-architectural and design solution for the revitalisation of the selected area of the Dražovce School site.	
Partners and stakeholders	elementary school Dražovce, Nitra Volunteer Centre, City of Nitra	

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Users and target groups	pupils of Elementary school Dražovce, parents and teachers
Co-deployment	The design process of the educational playground will be created in the form of a public call for proposals in cooperation with FHLE SUA, with teachers and students of FHLE SUA, children, teachers from Dražovce School and their parents. The implementation will take place in two phases. Some elements of the garden will be built together with parents of children, teachers, volunteers from Dražovce, the city and FHLE SUA, others will be procured.
Co-deployment – timeline	3/2022 - 12/2022 design of educational-play elements and procurement, 9/2022 - 12/2022 - first phase of realization, 4/2023 - 7/2023 second phase of realization
Co-management	Responsibility for the condition and safety of the educational playground will be assumed by the Dražovce Elementary School.

Zone	1, 2, 3, 4	
Locality	1.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 4.1, 4.3	River bank, City Park - Beaver's Yard, Swamp Biotope, Underpass, Entry to Dražovce, Elementary school Dražovce
Solutions	1.2.2, 2.3.4, 3.2.2, 3.4.2, 4.1.2, 4.3.4	
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>Innovative lighting solutions will be co-deployed along the already detailed hard VIS in most critical locations of the corridor. In location 1.2 on the river bank an autonomous (solar or wind powered) city lighting will be deployed with intelligent switch on sensor. For locations 2.3, 3.2 and 4.1 the lighting solutions will be integrated in other VIS elements deployed there (e.g. the pier, mobiliary elements) and with degree of luminosity should be considerate to wild animals, especially aquatic animals and insects. For locality 3.4 Underpass the lighting solutions should be deployed as an integrated part of the lighting art installation, with hanging or anchorable elements on the underpass ceiling and should be vandalism resistant. The same requirement is needed for the lighting solutions that will be deployed in residential area of Dražovce, where they will complement solutions deployed there.</p>	
Partners and stakeholders	SUA, City of Nitra, directly involved partners in relevant VIS	
Users and target groups	general public, cyclists, users of other relevant VIS	
Co-deployment	Most of the lighting solutions will be procured by SUA partner and co-deployed by SUA and NITRA partner, but also with stakeholders and partners involved in co-deployment process of VIS that are complemented by the relevant lighting solutions. In several locations new prototypes of autonomous lighting solutions will be tested.	
Co-deployment – timeline	Adapted to co-deployment timeline of relevant VIS	
Co-management	Maintenance will be carried out by the City of Nitra in case of deployment on their property, or those partners and stakeholders responsible for maintenance of VIS that are complemented by that specific lighting solution.	

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Appendix 15 Detailed descriptions of co-designed soft VIS and plans for their co-deployment and co-management

Solutions	1	Online IN-HUB platform
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>An online IN-HUB platform will be created, which will contain a summary of information of educational, informative and methodological nature on the individual VIS, proposed and implemented on the route: educational system connected to the community, therapeutic and experimental gardens (built in cooperation with the Botanical Garden, FHLE SUA and other relevant departments, Hidepark, NGO Cuketa, NGO Pestrec, etc.), systems for communication with users of the solutions and reservation systems (e.g. for the community kitchen, the workshop, the sauna, etc.). It will be managed by local community activators. The platform will also serve as a database of all types of outputs and individual processes of the individual VIS projects, with an aim to ensure the sustainability of the solutions after the end of the project.</p>	
Partners and stakeholders	IN-HUB core group (HIDE, SUA, NITRA)	
Users and target groups	the general public, specific groups, institutions and schools, visitors, professionals	
Co-deployment	<p>The online platform will be created on a separate website, the structure of which will be designed by the project team members together with the IT technician. Community activators (LCAs) will be tasked with adding individual content to the page in a phased manner as the projects progress, so that the evolution of the projects are captured in the online space, creating a database of all VISs and their solutions. The materials that will be added to the site will be: articles, blogs, video blogs, photos, educational materials, publications, streaming from the wildlife camera etc. All outputs will be added by the community activators in collaboration with the partners listed for each hard and soft solution.</p>	
Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025	

Solutions	2	Online living library
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<p>The online living library will be built from authentic individual stories of people from disadvantaged and excluded groups, their relatives and representatives of organisations or professionals working with these groups (in video, photo or other format). It will serve as an educational tool to combat prejudice and discrimination and as input material for co-design processes in the defined area (e.g. participatory co-design of inclusive play elements in playgrounds, inclusive elements of urban furniture, etc.). It will be gradually complemented by the stories of people and organisations involved in or impacted by the IN-HABIT project. The content</p>	

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	and the protagonists of the stories will be part of the discussion forums organised during the cultural activities (the classic model of a living library), while its online dimension will be housed on the online IN-HUB platform.
Partners and stakeholders	SUA, Hidepark, Independent Atelier 37, Mareena
Users and target groups	The public, specific groups, institutions and schools, professionals
Co-deployment	The stories will be created gradually throughout the INHABIT project. They will be collected by community activators (LCAs) and uploaded to the online INHABIT platform. For this project, we will collaborate with NGO Mareena, which has a library of stories from foreigners living all over the country. For the purpose of the INHABIT living library we will use those stories of Mareena that are related to foreigners living in Nitra. Subsequently, together with Mareena, we will organize several discussion forums and activities where we will invite these foreigners as speakers.
Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025

Solutions	3	Skills development and NBS and craft based entrepreneurship promotion
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	Providing low-threshold education and skills courses for the low-income and undereducated vulnerable groups with a focus on indoor greenery and green wall care, fruit tree care, experimental flower bed care, working with wood and textiles, upcycling and recycling.	
Partners and stakeholders	SUA, Botanical garden, NGO Cuketa, NGO Pestrec, Creative centre SUA, Creative centre Nitra, B2B	
Users and target groups	economic migrants, Roma community, low-income families	
Co-deployment	These courses will be used to acquire new, certified skills. It will therefore be important to organise them with the interest of the residents in mind. They will be conducted by certified experts and trainers in various fields. When organising the courses, we plan to cooperate with the SUS Creative Centre and the Nitra Creative Centre to select and share the individual courses and their lecturers in order to create a multiplier effect.	
Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025	

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Solutions	4	Platform for supporting local leaders and fundraising
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	A platform that will be used to educate active citizens in project management and fundraising in both the for-profit and non-profit sectors. Project partners will organize a series of lectures and workshops on the topics of setting up a civic association, the possibilities of obtaining grants from various private and public schemes, the characteristics of a good project, accounting, volunteer management, etc.	
Partners and stakeholders	IN-HUB	
Users and target groups	active citizens, NGOs, young people, communities	
Co-deployment	This platform will be led by members of the IN-HABIT team (WP4 local coordinator and LCA HIDE), who will act as lecturers at the individual lectures and workshops. In some cases, they will also invite other lecturers mainly from the non-profit sector. All materials will also be available within the Online INHAB platform. This process will be used to secure additional funding for VIS co-designed in Nitra pilot.	
Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025	

Solutions	5	Portfolio of educational activities, workshops and courses
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Workshop focused on native local tree species, their maintenance method and importance, justification in the biotope of the landscape 2. Education on the nature of the oat meadow, on flower composition and sowing meadows 3. Workshops for the preparation and planting of educational, therapeutic and experimental flower beds 4. Workshops to improve and expand craft skills, working with wood, metal and textiles and eco-friendly materials 5. Workshop for the preparation of raised beds 6. Workshop on building a traditional outdoor kiln from local clay or local materials 7. Workshop on building outdoor drying sheds for fruit and vegetables 8. Edible change workshops (ways of processing grown food - vegetables and fruits) 9. Educational workshops for the preparation of documentation for public space design processes 10. Discussion workshops on urban, rural and open landscape identity 11. Workshops on the creation of autonomous wind lighting with elements of object design 12. Ecological and design workshops at elementary schools 13. Floating flower bed design workshop 	

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	<p>14. Workshop on creating from waste materials</p> <p>15. Workshop on waste-free cooking / cooking from "waste" and public canteens</p> <p>16. Bicycle repair and maintenance workshop</p> <p>17. Drumming workshop (African and Brazilian drums)</p> <p>18. PechaKucha Nights (Japanese storytelling format) on topics of integration</p> <p>19. Workshop: Lets meet to understand</p> <p>20. Slovak language course for foreigners</p> <p>21. Language Café at Hidepark¹</p> <p>22. Art courses for adults</p> <p>23. Creative workshops (making theatre puppets, costumes, etc.)</p> <p>24. Photography and photo developing course</p> <p>25. Workshops on making simple musical (therapeutic) instruments - tailpiece, kalimba, djembe, etc.</p> <p>26. Workshop on linocut technique with printing of products (bags, etc.)</p> <p>27. Workshop of voice and movement techniques</p> <p>28. Dance workshops - Indian dances, Roma dances, etc.</p> <p>29. Outdoor education - offering special education for primary school pupils in a corridor setting on topics such as design, dendrology, ecology, sociology, floriculture/herbology</p>
Partners and stakeholders	SUA, HIDE, FHLE SUA, Botanical garden SUA, Institute of environmental management, Creative centre Nitra, Creative centre SUA, NGO Cuketa, NGO Pestrec, NGO Lets cycle Nitra!, Bikesharing Nitra, NGO HidePump, NGO I care, Bolf Kalimbas, NGO Drum show, NGO Mareena, Sekáč, NGO Independent atelier 37, Jana Ambrózová (UKF Folklore), ŠUP Nitra, Atelier Medea, OZ IRV/ROK
Users and target groups	all target groups
Co-deployment	Public workshops will be part of all the processes we propose in co-deployment and co-management of hard solutions, and they will be organized directly during the design and subsequent implementation, whether it is planting trees, creating an oatmeal meadow, planting diverse flowerbeds. In addition, we will prepare further workshops that will build on the solutions already co-deployed. In the community workshop at Hidepark, lecturers will teach how to work with wood, textiles, waste materials, etc. In the community garden, an expert will build a clay oven and a drying room for herbs and fruit, which will be used by all local gardeners. In the community kitchen, several courses on healthy eating and waste-free cooking will be held. Workshops on bike repair and maintenance will be held in the community bike workshop. In addition to workshops on manual dexterity, we will also offer art-based workshops on making various musical instruments, a course on drawing, a course on drumming, dancing, linocut printing, photo developing, etc. Most of these events will take place in Hidepark or in the Community centre in Dražovce, with sufficient technical equipment and facilities. All these workshops will be carried out by experts from among the above-mentioned partners and others. In addition, the community activators will also prepare community and cultural events for the general public, which will focus on topics such as inclusion in the form of talks, cafés and PechaKucha Nights. Educators from the FHLE SUA will prepare professional learning sessions that will be adapted to the needs of first and second grade students. In the field of dendrology, topics will be presented - distinguishing tree species by bark, fruits, and flowers. In the field of ecology, topics such as individual responsibility and the ecological city will be discussed.

¹ <https://languagevoices.eu/language-cafes/>

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Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025	
Solutions	6	Community events (for the general public)
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sunday chill at Hidepark - craft market, local DJs and foreign DJs, discussion about sustainable fashion, café world with Mareena (with foreigners), swap, theatre performances for children, workshops on theatre puppet making, workshops in the bike workshop 2. Market in Dražovce - Dražovisko - craft market 3. Trash collection in the corridor 4. Folkekokken kitchens- Danish concept of community dining where different cultures and stories come together, pop up dinners on the corridor 5. Community picnics on different themes with lots of activities (e.g. Meet Your Neighbor, World Cuisines Picnic, etc.) 	
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, NGO Independent atelier 37, Sekáč, NGO Mareena, NGO Lets cycle Nitra!, NGO HIDEpump	
Users and target groups	all target groups	
Co-deployment	Part of these events will take place in the Hidepark centre, where we will use the technical and material equipment of the centre. The production of the events will be carried out by community activators together with volunteers from the Hidepark and with volunteers from the Mareena association. In Dražovce, we will be holding a market for local residents, with production help from officers of the Department of Culture of the City of Nitra and the association of gardeners. We will also involve school children in the care of the corridor by collecting waste in critical polluted points of the corridor, followed by re-cycling.	
Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025	

Solutions	7	Sports and healthy lifestyle events
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Regular exercises for the public: yoga at Hidepark, Zumba at Hidepark, Spartan race, physiotherapy exercises 2. Cruising on the Nitra River through boat rental 3. Activities at the public sauna on wheels in the city park 4. Cooling off in the lake in the city park with the IceBears community 5. Participation in the initiative Running through Evening Nitra - along the corridor 6. Cycling breakfast on the newly constructed cycle route City Park - Industrial Park 	

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Partners and stakeholders	HIDE, NGO Lets cycle Nitra!, NGO HIDEPump, Adoreal s.r.o., NGO Icebears, community Night run Nitra, NGO Cuketa, certified lecturers
Users and target groups	all target groups
Co-deployment	Regular exercises at Hidepark will be conducted on a weekly basis by certified instructors. Boat rentals will be operated during the summer months by the HIDE partner, namely the centres manager. Use of the public sauna and hardening sessions will be organised by the IceBears Association during the winter months. The association Lets cycle Nitra! in cooperation with community activators will implement a series of cycling breakfasts that serve as a motivation for the use of the bicycle as a means of transport to work.
Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025

Solutions	8	Art events/interventions
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Artistic site specific residency with the participation of the IN-HUB group 2. Series of public art exhibitions in the spaces under the bridge - underpass 3. Participatory photography 4. Concerts of foreigners living in Slovakia 5. Theatrical performances with an educational dimension for children 6. Movie evenings with discussions 	
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, NGO Independent atelier 37, NGO Mareena, Elementary school Dražovce, Elementary school Tulipánová, local artists, Morgonrock, Nové divadlo, Divadelné centrum Martin	
Users and target groups	all target groups	
Co-deployment	<p>Most of the artistic events will take place in the Hidepark centre, which meets the standards of an independent cultural centre, both in terms of technical equipment, staff and know-how. Members of the Hidepark crew, in collaboration with community activators and appointed partners, will design the centre's dramaturgy to meet the requirements of the IN-HABIT project. This will include concert performances by foreigners living in Slovakia, movie evenings with discussions on various topics such as inclusion, healthy lifestyles, integration, etc., theatre performances with an educational dimension for children and young people, and the installation of a site-specific art and objects that will be created as a product of the participatory art residency. In addition to the Hidepark, we will also work on art installations under the bridge to make this neglected place visually more attractive. In the participatory photography project, we will offer photographic cameras, which are easy to use, to our photographers from marginalized communities and IN-HUB members, in order to capture key aspects of their lives in the city and during the project. The instructor will prepare several group photo sessions to explain the basics of photography. The photographs will then be exhibited in the Community centre in Dražovce and at selected locations along the corridor.</p>	

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Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025
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Solutions	9	Special dramaturgy in Community centre of Dražovce
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Theatre performances for adults and children 2. PechaKucha Nights/conversations 3. Dražovisko - market in front of the Community centre 4. Temporary art/photography installation 5. Movie screenings 	
Partners and stakeholders	Hidepark, Elementary school Tulipánova, Department of Culture of the City of Nitra, Kinoklub Nitra	
Users and target groups	all target groups	
Co-deployment	The regular dramaturgy of the Dražovce Community centre will be set together with the Department of Culture of the City of Nitra, which owns it. During events we will use technical equipment, which also belongs to the property of the City of Nitra. The production of these events will be the responsibility of the cultural officer of the Department of Culture in cooperation with community activators.	
Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025	

Solutions	10	Publication activity
Innovations		
Description of solutions, qualitative and technical requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Manual of participative planning 2. Conference activity (Conference_city/field/village) 3. Catalogues of design processes 4. Educational materials for primary schools 5. Educational materials for universities 6. Roma cookbook in cooperation with Dražovce Elementary School teachers 	
Partners and stakeholders	SUA, HIDE, Botanical garden SUA, Institute of Environmental Management, Creative Centre Nitra, Creative Centre SUA, NGO Cuketa, NGO Pestrec, NGO Lets cycle Nitra!, NGO Mareena, NGO Independent atelier 37, OZ IRV/ROK, Elementary school Dražovce and others	
Co-deployment	Mostly based on bilateral cooperation agreements	
Co-deployment – timeline	2022 - 2025	

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